

GenderSAFE
ENDING GENDER-BASED VIOLENCE IN ACADEMIA

A Safer European Research Area

Full Report on National Policies to Counteract Gender-Based Violence

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SUMMARY

Objectives and scope: This report supports European Research Area coordination on counteracting gender-based violence in research and innovation and higher education by (i) mapping national policy instruments addressing gender-based violence; (ii) analysing the comprehensiveness of national policy frameworks and their alignment with the 2024 Zero-Tolerance Code of Conduct across the three pillars (Commitment, Action, Accountability); (iii) identifying gaps and areas where policy design remains underdeveloped or insufficiently operationalised; (iv) documenting recent and ongoing policy developments; and (v) informing future EU-level coordination by highlighting policy needs and opportunities for further alignment. The intended coverage was EU-27 and Associated Countries engaged in ERA governance; 18 countries submitted complete responses in this reporting cycle.

Methodology in brief: Data were collected via the GenderSAFE Task 5.4 questionnaire administered through LimeSurvey between 13 October and 16 December 2025, supported by guidance, reminders and bilateral follow-up. The questionnaire was the primary data source. Respondents provided information on the national policy and legislative framework with links to the documents where available; for in-depth analysis, the respondents selected the main policy instrument for which detailed information was provided, including on aspects related to the recommendations in the three pillars of the Zero-Tolerance Code of Conduct. The GenderSAFE team conducted a targeted document review of some of the shared instruments to clarify ambiguities and support consistent coding. They also double-checked information about the instruments with respondents, including the policy comprehensiveness coding. To assess policy comprehensiveness, indicators were applied using predefined rules and thresholds across a five-category scale (Comprehensive, Developing, Intermediary, Emerging, Absent). For pillar-level analysis (Commitment/Action/Accountability), only countries with dedicated instruments addressing R&I and higher education were included (N=12).

Key findings: The policy landscape is highly differentiated across the 18 European countries assessed. Five countries have a comprehensive instrument mix (Belgium, France, Ireland, the Netherlands, Portugal), while four are developing (Austria, Czechia, Denmark, Poland), three intermediary (Lithuania, Sweden, Norway), four emerging (Croatia, Slovakia, Albania, Iceland) and two absent (Bulgaria, Finland). A key cross-cutting pattern is that general equality/anti-discrimination and violence against women frameworks are widespread but do not automatically translate into policies specific to higher education and research and innovation institutions. Recent evolution often takes the form of policy layering, whereby new policy measures are added to existing frameworks rather than replacing them, with visible acceleration since 2023 in several contexts.

Commitment pillar: The indicator synthesis identifies Commitment as the weakest pillar. No country reaches “comprehensive” or “developing” commitment under the current operationalisation. Eight countries are intermediary (Austria, Czechia, France, Ireland, the Netherlands, Portugal, Sweden, Norway) and four are absent (Belgium, Denmark, Lithuania, Poland). This indicates that explicit recognition of the systemic nature of gender-based violence, priority groups, and defined principles of the zero-tolerance approach are not consistently embedded in national policy design, even where instruments exist.

Action pillar: No country reaches “comprehensive” action. Five countries are developing (Belgium, Denmark, France, Ireland, Portugal), four intermediary (Czechia, Lithuania, the Netherlands, Sweden), one emerging (Austria), and two absent (Poland, Norway). Overall, the breadth of measures across the 7P framework remains incomplete.

Accountability pillar: The indicator synthesis identifies Accountability as the pillar with the widest spread but remains underdeveloped in most countries. Four countries are classified as “comprehensive” (Austria, France, Ireland, and Sweden), six countries are classified as “emerging” (Czechia, Denmark, the Netherlands, Norway, Poland, and Portugal), and two as “absent” (Belgium, Lithuania). This suggests that in many countries, policies may encourage or require institutional action, but often lack system-level monitoring, reporting, evaluation, and enforcement to sustain implementation over time.

Policy outlook: The outlook is predominantly strengthening: nine countries report a strengthened outlook (Austria, Belgium, Croatia, Czechia, France, Ireland, the Netherlands, Portugal, Albania), eight unchanged (Bulgaria, Denmark, Finland, Poland, Slovakia, Sweden, Iceland, Norway), and none regressing. Most significantly, the policy evolution takes the form of legislative strengthening in the Netherlands with the introduction of a legal duty of care and policy review/renewal cycles in Ireland and France.

Key policy messages:

- **Focus attention on advancing the Commitment dimension**, by strengthening the recognition of gender-based violence as a systemic issue, ensuring comprehensive coverage of priority groups, and embedding clear zero-tolerance principles in national policy frameworks.
- **Strengthen dedicated sector-specific (R&I and higher education) policies:** Where only general frameworks exist, develop instruments or structured support programmes focused on R&I and higher education that clarify institutional responsibilities toward staff and students across organisational types.
- **Provide longer-term sustainable resourcing:** Make financing clear and transparent and ensure that resources reach institutions to operationalise prevention, support services, and robust procedures along the entire 7P framework.
- **Continue to use mutual learning and coordination mechanisms** (ERA governance, Communities of Practice) to disseminate policy advances and lessons learnt beyond the current core of active countries.

Limitations: The monitoring is based primarily on self-reported information from national authorities and does not assess implementation effectiveness or impact. Coverage is incomplete (as not all countries participated), cross-country legal/terminology differences affect comparability, the policy field is dynamic, and sub-national variation is currently only partially (Belgium) or not (Germany) captured in devolved systems.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

7P	7P model: policy, prevalence, prevention, protection, prosecution, partnership, provision of services
AC	Associated Countries to Horizon Europe
AL	Albania
AT	Austria
BE	Belgium
BG	Bulgaria
CZ	Czechia
DK	Denmark
ERA	European Research Area
EU	European Union
FR	France
FI	Finland
GEP	Gender Equality Plan
GBV	Gender-Based Violence
HE	Higher Education
HEI(s)	Higher education institution(s)
HR	Croatia
IE	Ireland
IS	Iceland
LGBTQIA+	Lesbian, gay, bisexual, trans, queer/questioning, intersex, asexual, and other

LT	Lithuania
MS	Member States of the European Union
NGO(s)	Non-governmental organisation(s)
NL	Netherlands
NO	Norway
PL	Poland
PT	Portugal
R&I	Research and Innovation
SE	Sweden
SK	Slovakia
UN	United Nations
UNHCR	United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees

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1. INTRODUCTION

This report directly supports EU efforts to advance the implementation of EU-wide action to counteract gender-based violence in the European Research Area (ERA). It builds on the results of the [ERA Policy Agenda 2022–2024](#), notably Action 5 “Promote gender equality and foster inclusiveness”, and specifically the [Zero-Tolerance Code of Conduct](#) (European Commission, 2024) developed by the ERA Forum Sub-group on Inclusive Gender Equality, in close cooperation with the European Commission. The Code consolidates state-of-the-art expectations for the research and innovation (R&I) and higher education system, explicitly emphasising the gendered and systemic nature of violence, unequal power relations, and the need for victim-centred and trauma-informed approaches, while strengthening attention to comprehensive organisational response, leadership responsibility, and accountability.

This report contributes to EU policy coordination by mapping and analysing national policy instruments in place to counteract gender-based violence against the recommendations set out in the Zero-Tolerance Code of Conduct and by identifying gaps in policy design that hinder consistent progress across the ERA. At the same time, it is forward-looking: it is intended to inform the current [ERA Policy Agenda 2025–2027](#) and its continued focus on inclusive gender equality, including the further uptake and implementation of the Code across Member States, Associated Countries, and key R&I stakeholders.

1.1 POLICY AND LEGAL CONTEXT

Over the past decade, policy attention to gender-based violence in higher education and research and innovation has increased significantly at EU, national and institutional levels. This evolution reflects both the accumulation of robust research evidence on its prevalence and consequences (Humbert et al., 2024; Humbert and Strid, 2024), its scholarly theorisation for R&I and higher education, and the understanding of the complexity of responses needed to effectively counteract it, reflected in the Zero-Tolerance Code of Conduct.

Research evidence and conceptual development underpinning ERA Action 5

The ERA-level advances described above have been supported by conceptual development and evidence building, including through the Horizon 2020 UniSAFE project (2021–2024). UniSAFE adopted a comprehensive approach that combined conceptual development (Strid et al. 2021; Mergaert et al., 2023) with a large-scale European quantitative study (over 42,000 respondents) (Lipinsky et al., 2022a, 2022b), national policy analysis (Fajmonová et al., 2021), a qualitative analysis of institutional policies (Huck et al., 2022), research on institutional response (Ranea-Triviño, 2022), and individual experiences of violence (Blazyte & Pilinkaite Sotirovic, 2023). UniSAFE also produced a toolkit that brings together methodological resources and policy advice tailored to the needs of diverse stakeholders across the sector (UniSAFE Zenodo Community, 2024).

ERA instruments translating commitments into organisational practice

Alongside the Zero-Tolerance Code of Conduct, several ERA instruments support the implementation of actions to counteract gender-based violence. The revised [European](#)

[Charter for Researchers](#) (annexed to the Council Recommendation adopted in December 2023) explicitly integrates gender-based violence and sexual harassment, including expectations that employers in the ERA provide working conditions that promote wellbeing and include appropriate procedures for preventing and tackling gender-based violence. The **HR Excellence in Research Award** (HRS4R Award) provides a structured mechanism through which Research Performing Organisations (RPOs) demonstrate progress in implementing Charter principles in institutional policies and practices, supported by assessment and renewal processes.

Furthermore, the **Gender Equality Plan** (GEP) eligibility criterion in Horizon Europe has contributed to consolidating institutional action on gender equality. Importantly, the eligibility criterion explicitly lists “measures against gender-based violence, including sexual harassment” among the recommended thematic areas to be addressed in GEPs. This has created stronger incentives for institutions to adopt and formalise measures and contributed to the diffusion of relevant policies, tools and roles (e.g., confidential counsellors, ombuds structures, updated procedures and reporting mechanisms).

An expanded stakeholder engagement in the ERA

Importantly, the stakeholder landscape has broadened substantially. Policy engagement on gender-based violence now extends beyond the European Commission and national authorities to include European Research Funding Organisations (RFOs), ERA umbrella organisations, and a growing range of higher education and research institutions. This expanding engagement indicates a move toward increasing shared ownership, while also underscoring the importance of coordination, coherence and mutual learning across different governance levels.

Broader EU and international policy evolution

At the level of overarching EU policy, ending gender-based violence has been positioned as a key objective under the European Commission’s [Gender Equality Strategy 2020–2025](#), adopted on 8 March 2020 as a core element of the Union of Equality. The strategy states that the EU will do all it can to prevent and combat gender-based violence, support and protect victims, and hold perpetrators accountable, while also calling on **Member States to systematically collect and report data on gender-based violence**. This commitment has been reaffirmed in subsequent policy initiatives, including the European Commission’s [Roadmap for Women’s Rights](#), which outlines the Union’s continued priorities for advancing gender equality and strengthening action against gender-based violence across the EU. On 6 March 2026, the European Commission published the [Gender Equality Strategy 2026 – 2030](#), which affirms the commitment to eradicating gender-based violence, in cooperation with Member States, focusing newly on cyberviolence and gender-based violence in the framework of the Digital Services Act.

At the level of EU law, harassment and sexual harassment in employment contexts have long been addressed through [Council Directive 2006/54/EC \(Equal Treatment Directive\)](#), which prohibits harassment and sexual harassment as forms of discrimination. In addition, the EU formally acceded in June 2023 to the Council of Europe’s Istanbul Convention (Convention on preventing and combating violence against women and domestic violence), which entered into force for the EU on 1 October 2023. At national level, all EU Member States have signed the Convention, and a majority have ratified it. These frameworks have

reinforced shared standards and have contributed to harmonising expectations around prevention, protection, and support.

Most recently, a further step was the adoption of [Directive \(EU\) 2024/1385 on combating violence against women and domestic violence](#), which entered into force in 2024 with a transposition deadline of 14 June 2027. The directive introduces measures to prevent violence against women and domestic violence, sets standards for victim protection, and criminalises specific forms of violence including female genital mutilation, forced marriage, non-consensual sharing of intimate images, cyber stalking, cyber harassment, and cyber incitement to hatred or violence. Importantly, it also specifies detailed rules on assistance and protection measures to be provided by Member States, reinforcing the victim-centred approach that is increasingly recognised as essential.

Beyond EU instruments, international developments also point towards stronger commitments in the world of work and the role of broader structural factors. The [Council decision No. 2024/1018 inviting Member States to ratify the ILO Violence and Harassment Convention, 2019 \(No. 190\)](#) advanced in early 2024 and was supported by relevant committees of the European Parliament, with rapporteurs underlining that violence and harassment are linked to wider societal issues including power relations, gender norms, cultural and social norms, discrimination, and stigmatisation.

1.2 OBJECTIVES OF THE REPORT

The monitoring presented in this report is designed to contribute to the ERA structural policy on inclusive gender equality by providing evidence on national policy frameworks, identifying advances and continued gaps, and supporting mutual learning across Member States (MS) and Associated Countries (AC). In doing so, this report aims to strengthen the evidence base for European coordination on gender-based violence in higher education and research and innovation.

The primary intended use is to inform (i) ERA-level coordination (European Commission and Member States) and (ii) policy dialogue and mutual learning among national authorities, research funding organisations and ERA stakeholder organisations and research performing organisations, including through the ERA Forum Sub-group on Inclusive Gender Equality and the [GenderSAFE Community of Practice](#).

Against this background, the **report objectives** are to:

1. **Map national policy instruments** addressing gender-based violence in higher education and research and innovation across MS and AC, based on data collected through the GenderSAFE Task 5.4 national questionnaire.
2. **Analyse policy comprehensiveness** by examining the extent to which national instruments address (a) commitment, (b) action across the 7P framework, and (c) accountability recommendations in the Zero-Tolerance Code of Conduct.
3. **Assess alignment and identify gaps in policy design in relation to the Zero-Tolerance Code of Conduct's recommendations**, highlighting recurring areas where policies appear underdeveloped, inconsistent, or insufficiently operationalised.

4. **Provide a forward-looking policy outlook** by documenting policy developments underway and new initiatives, while identifying potential opportunities and risks for further policy evolution at EU and national levels.
5. **Develop recommendations for EU-level coordination and future policy needs**, indicating where further alignment, guidance, monitoring or support mechanisms may be needed to advance progress across the ERA.

Scope and limitations. The monitoring focuses on national level **policy design and adoption**. The intended coverage was the EU-27 and AC engaged in the ERA Forum. However, not all countries provided data. The report is based primarily on **self-reported information** provided by national authorities and does not constitute an evaluation of the actual implementation or the effectiveness of measures; these limitations are discussed in detail in the Methodology section.

1.3 RESEARCH QUESTIONS AND TARGET AUDIENCES

This report addresses the **following questions**:

- What national policy instruments on gender-based violence in R&I and higher education are in place across the EU and AC?
- To what extent do these instruments reflect zero-tolerance principles, a victim-centred and trauma-informed approach, and other commitment principles outlined in the Zero-Tolerance Code of Conduct?
- To what extent do these instruments reflect the recommended actions along the 7P framework and accountability recommendations?
- What is the policy outlook (policy strengthening, policy weakening) in R&I and higher education in the ERA?
- What policy developments are foreseen in the near future?

Target audience

The report is intended primarily for:

- ERA-level stakeholders, including the European Commission and MS and AC representatives engaged in ERA governance, to support coordination and monitoring under the ERA structural policy on inclusive gender equality and to inform the further uptake of the Zero-Tolerance Code of Conduct as part of ongoing ERA policy implementation, including the negotiation of the ERA Act.
- National authorities and ministries responsible for research, higher education, and gender equality, as well as RFOs, as a resource for comparative insight, mutual learning, and the identification of further opportunities for policy advancement.

The report provides an overview of policy instruments and gaps that can inform discussion in the ERA Forum Sub-group on Inclusive Gender Equality and the existing GenderSAFE Community of Practice. It can serve as a baseline for future follow-up work, including further initiatives building on GenderSAFE and related projects.

Second, the report may also be useful for other stakeholders with an interest in national policy evolution, including R&I and higher education umbrella organisations and institutional actors seeking to situate internal policies within the broader national and European policy environment.

1.4 STRUCTURE OF THE REPORT

The report is structured as follows: the **Summary** presents the key findings, gaps and policy implications in relation to the Zero-Tolerance Code of Conduct. The **Introduction** situates the monitoring in the ERA Policy Agenda and relevant EU policy frameworks and outlines the objectives, research questions, and target audience. The **Theoretical framing** introduces the key conceptual elements that have informed this analysis, including the Zero-Tolerance Code of Conduct, the 7P framework, intersectionality, inclusiveness and priority groups, and victim- and survivor-centred and trauma-informed approaches. The **Methodology** explains the monitoring design, data collection, the coding and classification framework, and methodological considerations, including ethics, data handling, and limitations. The **Results** section synthesises the instruments in place and assesses alignment with the Code's pillars of Commitment, Action, and Accountability, including a forward-looking policy outlook, while **cross-cutting themes and qualitative insights** contextualise the indicator-based findings. The **Conclusions** summarise implications and recommendations and reflect on lessons for future monitoring. **References and the Appendix** provide full documentation of sources, definitions, and supporting materials.

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

This report is grounded in the *Zero-Tolerance Code of Conduct: Counteracting gender-based violence, including sexual harassment, in the EU research and innovation system* (European Commission, 2024). Developed as a deliverable of Action 5 ‘Promote gender equality and foster inclusiveness’ of the ERA Policy Agenda 2022–2024 by the ERA Forum Sub-group on Inclusive Gender Equality, the Zero-Tolerance Code of Conduct provides a shared conceptual and normative reference point for counteracting gender-based violence across the ERA and clarifies roles and responsibilities at EU, national, funding, and institutional levels.

Zero tolerance and the three-pillar structure

The Zero-Tolerance Code of Conduct advances a zero-tolerance approach to gender-based violence. In the context of R&I and higher education, zero tolerance means treating the full continuum of behaviours as unacceptable and actionable, recognising that “less visible” forms of harm (including everyday discriminatory conduct and micro-aggressions) contribute to an enabling climate for more severe violence and harassment, and therefore require institutional and policy attention.

To operationalise zero tolerance, the Code of Conduct is structured around three interlinked pillars (Commitment, Action, and Accountability), which together articulate what a comprehensive approach should entail:

- **Commitment** concerns the recognition of gender-based violence as a systemic issue rooted in unequal power relations and organisational cultures, and the articulation of clear principles that establish key elements that need to inform policy design and implementation.
- **Action** concerns the translation of commitment into concrete measures across the full spectrum of prevention and response, procedures, capacity building, support and protection for victims/survivors, and collaboration arrangements along the 7P framework.
- **Accountability** concerns mechanisms that ensure implementation, oversight, monitoring and appropriate consequences, including clear responsibilities, reporting and investigation arrangements, and institutional leadership accountability for safe study and work environments.

This pillar structure provides the backbone for the report’s analytical logic and supports comparative assessment across diverse national policy instruments.

The 7P framework as the backbone of the “Action” pillar

The Action pillar is informed by the **7P model** developed in the UniSAFE project (Strid et al., 2021; Mergaert et al., 2023). The 7P framework addresses gender-based violence not as an isolated individualised issue but as a systemic institutional and policy challenge requiring coordinated intervention across seven dimensions:

1. **Policy**
2. **Prevalence**
3. **Prevention**

4. **Protection**
5. **Prosecution** (including internal disciplinary measures)
6. **Provision of services**
7. **Partnerships**

In this report, the 7P framework underpins the operationalisation of the Action pillar by ensuring that the monitoring captures the breadth of measures needed for effective prevention and response.

Intersectionality, inclusiveness, and priority groups

An **intersectional perspective** is central to understanding how gender-based violence manifests itself in R&I and higher education systems and how policies enable or hinder effective support and protection. Intersectionality highlights that experiences of violence, barriers to reporting, and access to institutional protection are shaped by the interplay of multiple structural inequalities, including (among others) gender, race/ethnicity, (im)migration status, disability, sexual orientation, socioeconomic background, age, and contractual and hierarchical position within academia. This approach moves beyond an additive understanding of multiple grounds of inequality and instead focuses on how overlapping systems of disadvantage shape who is exposed to harm and who can access support and redress. The Zero-Tolerance Code of Conduct explicitly embeds intersectional considerations in its framing and definitions.

Within this conceptual framework, this report uses the term **priority groups** to refer to populations that policies explicitly identify as requiring particular attention due to structurally heightened exposure to gender-based violence and/or barriers to support. This terminology is used deliberately to emphasise structural conditions and institutional power imbalances, rather than implying inherent vulnerability. Assessing whether and how policies recognise priority groups forms a crucial element of analysing inclusiveness and alignment with intersectional principles.

Victim-/survivor-centred and trauma-informed approaches

A victim-/survivor-centred approach prioritises listening, stresses the avoidance of re-traumatisation, focuses on safety and well-being, supports autonomy and choice, and aims to restore as much control to the victim/survivor as is feasible throughout the process. It is widely reflected in international guidance (UN Women 2019; UNHCR 2024; European Institute for Gender Equality 2024) and aligns with the Victims' Rights Directive (European Commission 2024). The shift towards a victim-/survivor-centred approach reflects the growing recognition of victim/survivor needs and the failures of punitive, re-traumatising approaches, a better understanding of the impact of trauma, and an emphasis on long-term healing (UN Women 2019; UNHCR 2024; European Institute for Gender Equality 2024). The victim-/survivor-centred approach is central to the Commitment pillar of the Zero-Tolerance Code of Conduct, which emphasises that effective responses to gender-based violence in R&I and higher education require approaches that put the needs, rights, and safety of victims/survivors at the centre.

A trauma-informed approach is closely related and builds on the “do no harm” principle, seeking to maximise physical, psychological and emotional safety, prevent re-traumatisation and secondary victimisation, and avoid stereotypical assumptions about how

victims/survivors “should” respond. It typically foregrounds safety, trustworthiness, choice, collaboration, and empowerment as practical principles for institutional procedures and services. Acknowledging that victims/survivors can manifest a diverse array of reactions and responses, it underscores the importance of rejecting stereotypical notions about victims/survivors in order to ensure comprehensive support for all in need and to accurately gauge the level of trauma and distress experienced (National SART Guidelines Development Group 2023). The goal of a trauma-informed approach is to care for the victim/survivor and assist in the initiation of the healing process. It emphasises understanding the prevalence and effects of trauma, promoting safety and trust, and empowering victims/survivors to regain control over their lives.

Multilevel governance, policy mixes, and accountability in implementation

Gender-based violence governance in higher education and in research and innovation is shaped by multilevel policy mixes: national legislation and strategies, soft-law instruments and guidance, sector frameworks, and organisational policies (including Gender Equality Plans and related institutional procedures). These instruments interact, sometimes reinforcing one another, sometimes creating gaps and/or inconsistencies. In the ERA context, this interaction is particularly visible in the way the Code of Conduct (as an ERA deliverable) is linked to broader instruments shaping research careers and organisational standards (e.g., the Charter framework and the GEP).

At the same time, this report draws a clear conceptual line between **the presence of instruments** (policy adoption and design) and **their implementation and enforcement**. The monitoring focuses primarily on the former: what frameworks exist and how they are designed. It recognises that meaningful impact depends on resourcing, monitoring, enforcement mechanisms, and institutional leadership accountability. This distinction is reflected in the report design: Accountability is analysed as a core pillar, but the report does not evaluate implementation outcomes in practice, which would require different data sources and methods.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 DATA COLLECTION

Data source and sample. Data for this report were collected through an online questionnaire developed within the national monitoring methodology (GenderSAFE Deliverable 5.1) and implemented through GenderSAFE's Task 5.4 launch and roll-out process. The questionnaire serves as the core monitoring tool for capturing national policy adoption and formal policy design addressing gender-based violence in R&I and higher education. It was administered via LimeSurvey, enabling structured data collection, secure data storage, and controlled access for respondents.

The monitoring exercise received responses from 18 countries. Of these, 15 are EU Member States (Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czechia, Denmark, Finland, France, Ireland, Lithuania, the Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Slovakia, and Sweden) and three are Associated or candidate countries (Albania, Iceland and Norway). In relative terms, this corresponds to 15 out of 27 EU Member States and three out of the 17 Associated or candidate countries eligible under the ERA governance structure.

Participation also included countries classified under the Widening framework. Of the 15 EU Widening countries, seven contributed to the national mapping, while one country participated among the 14 Associated Widening Countries.

Target population and respondents. The target population consisted of national public authorities in EU MS and AC with responsibility for higher education and/or R&I policy. The questionnaire was disseminated primarily through the ERA Forum Sub-group on Inclusive Gender Equality. Sub-group members were invited to respond directly or to coordinate internally with other competent ministries and authorities, depending on national governance and portfolio division.

Federal/decentralised systems. In federal or decentralised systems (Belgium, Germany), the data collection was intended to reflect national-level frameworks in conjunction with regional competences where relevant. In the present report, the analysis focuses on national-level submissions only. Germany's regional-level input is being collected separately and will be analysed and reported at a later stage; the questionnaire therefore remains open for that purpose.

Data collection period and coverage. The initial data collection period ran from 13 October 2025 to 14 November 2025 and was supported by completion guidance. Reminder emails were circulated during the collection period to encourage completion. Deadlines were extended for several respondents upon request to support participation. The final submission included in this analysis was received on 16 December 2025. A total of 18 countries submitted completed questionnaires for this reporting cycle. Countries that did not submit a response were recorded as "No data."

Support to respondents. To maximise participation and enhance consistency, the project team provided written guidance (glossary, completion instructions, and FAQs), a helpdesk function, and the possibility of online consultations.

Nature of the data. The monitoring is based primarily on **self-reported** information provided by responsible national authorities through the questionnaire. It captures the

presence and key characteristics of policy instruments (laws, strategies, regulations, guidance, and initiatives) addressing gender-based violence in R&I and higher education, as well as reported features relevant to alignment with the Zero-Tolerance Code of Conduct. The monitoring focuses on **policy adoption and design** and does not constitute an assessment of implementation, the effectiveness of measures, or impact.

Unit of analysis. The primary unit of analysis is the **country**. Within each country, the analysis considers a policy mix (i.e., the set of national instruments reported as relevant to gender-based violence in R&I and higher education, rather than treating single instruments in isolation). For analytical purposes, reported instruments were grouped into broad categories (e.g., dedicated instruments that focus on addressing gender-based violence in higher education and research; general instruments addressing gender-based violence such as higher education laws or policies or research and innovation laws or policies as well as more general laws and policies that address violence against women, or gender equality), enabling comparative assessment of policy comprehensiveness and alignment across diverse governance contexts.

Types of instruments analysed. The classification of national instruments into dedicated laws, dedicated policies, general laws, general policies, and initiatives was conducted in line with the operational definitions set out in the GenderSAFE monitoring methodology. Although national authorities self-identified their instruments in the questionnaire, the project team systematically reviewed all links and documents provided to ensure conceptual consistency across countries. Where the title of an instrument did not clearly indicate a focus on research and innovation or higher education, the document was examined in detail to determine whether gender-based violence in these sectors was explicitly and specifically addressed. This review enabled a distinction between instruments addressing or at least mentioning higher education and research, and those addressing broader frameworks, such as general gender equality or violence against women policies without an explicit mention of the issue of gender-based violence in higher education and/or R&I. Where discrepancies between self-classification and the operational definitions were identified, instruments were reclassified according to the predefined criteria. Definitions were made available to national authorities through a glossary and supporting materials, and clarification was offered during the data collection period. Lastly, the final classification was reviewed and confirmed by national authorities, ensuring both harmonisation and validation of the categorisation.

Verification and document review. The Task 5.4 questionnaire was the primary data source. Respondents were required to provide the titles, ownership information, and, where available, public links to relevant laws, policies, and initiatives. These links were reviewed to clarify ambiguities and to ensure consistency in the coding and classification of instruments. While the methodology relies primarily on self-reported data, several measures were taken to enhance accuracy and internal consistency. The project team conducted a targeted document review of publicly available sources for selected instruments where clarification was needed (e.g., to confirm basic scope, responsible actors, or the existence of key provisions relevant to the coding framework). This verification was used to resolve ambiguities in questionnaire entries, harmonise terminology across countries, and support consistent classification of instrument types. Final validation of the submitted information remained with the respective national authorities, who were given the opportunity to review and confirm their responses prior to analysis.

Operationalisation and coding framework. The monitoring framework operationalises the Zero-Tolerance Code of Conduct through three analytical pillars (Commitment, Action, and Accountability) and translates questionnaire responses into a set of rule-based indicators designed for cross-country comparison. The coding framework and thresholds were defined ex ante in the GenderSAFE monitoring methodology (Deliverable 5.1) and applied consistently across the responding countries. Detailed decision rules, thresholds, and item mappings are provided in **Appendix 1**.

The analysis uses a five-category maturity scale (**Comprehensive, Developing, Intermediary, Emerging, Absent**) to classify (i) the overall national policy framework (“instrument mix”) and (ii) alignment with each of the three pillars. This scale is intended to support policy interpretation and mutual learning by distinguishing between contexts with dedicated instruments, contexts relying primarily on general frameworks and/or initiatives, and contexts where policy attention remains limited or non-specific to R&I and higher education.

Operationalisation of indicators. The report presents five indicators based on a graded scale of categories to provide an overview of national developments and alignment with the Code of Conduct. First, the **overall comprehensiveness of the national legal and policy framework** captures the presence and configuration of dedicated instruments, general instruments, and initiatives. Second, the **policy outlook** indicator captures reported plans to strengthen, maintain, or weaken policies, based on the responses and where applicable conservative interpretation of “Other” entries supported by respondent explanations. Third to fifth, the report presents respective indicators for the three pillars that assess alignment with the Code of Conduct’s structure: **Commitment** (systemic framing, priority groups/protected characteristics, and zero-tolerance principles), **Action** (institutional measures across the 7P framework), and **Accountability** (system-level oversight, reporting, monitoring/evaluation, leadership responsibility, and sanctions). For each indicator, countries are assigned to a category according to predefined rules and cut-offs; no post-hoc adjustments were made. The graded scale format is used to support readability and navigation for policy audiences and is visually represented through colour coding, where **green indicates the most comprehensive or strengthening policy developments, purple indicates weakening developments, and blue represents neutral or intermediate categories**. Full technical specifications are provided in Appendix 1.

Ethics and data protection: The data collected for this monitoring exercise relate primarily to national public policies, laws, and initiatives addressing gender-based violence in R&I and higher education. The questionnaire also collects professional contact details of the respondents appointed to complete the survey and may include descriptive information that could identify individuals acting in their professional capacity. These contact details are kept separate from the analytical dataset, are accessible only to authorised members of the Task 5.4 analytical team and are not shared beyond the project team.

Participation by national authorities was fully informed and voluntary, supported by Terms of Use that set out the purpose of data collection, processing conditions, and participants’ rights under the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). Personal data were processed lawfully based on explicit consent and handled in accordance with GDPR and

applicable Czech data protection legislation. Raw data were stored securely on password-protected servers with access restricted to authorised GenderSAFE team members.

Only information at country level is reported in this analysis, and no personal identifiers or sensitive institutional details beyond publicly available information are disclosed. Personal data of the responsible representatives were only used for confirmation of the analysis' results, document classification, and policy information verification. It will be retained for the duration of the project and deleted thereafter in line with the project's data retention schedule. Processing complied with the internal ethics and data protection procedures of the Institute of Sociology of the Czech Academy of Sciences, including oversight by the institutional Data Protection Officer.

3.2 DATA PROCESSING AND VALIDATION

After closure of the data collection period, questionnaire responses were exported from LimeSurvey and underwent a structured data cleaning and validation process. Submissions were reviewed for internal consistency and coherence across sections (e.g., consistency between reported instruments and subsequent answers on Commitment, Action, and Accountability). Where ambiguities, inconsistencies, or unclear "Other" responses were identified, the project team contacted the relevant national authority (using the contact details provided) to request clarification. To reduce interpretative divergence and support comparability, terminology was standardised through the glossary and definitions in the questionnaire. Open-ended responses were analysed qualitatively to provide contextual information; however, qualitative text was not used to override structured responses unless it explicitly clarified the respondent's intended interpretation of an item.

3.3 HANDLING MISSING AND PARTIAL DATA

Unit of analysis and inclusion criteria. The unit of analysis is the national-level policy framework (country level). Only one submission per country was included in the dataset. In countries with regional differentiation or devolved competences, the monitoring focused during this cycle on the national-level response submitted through the designated national authority. Only fully submitted questionnaires were included in the analysis; draft or partially completed submissions were not analysed.

Non-response and missing items. Countries that did not submit a questionnaire were excluded from analytical calculations and visualisations and recorded uniformly as "No data." In visual representations (e.g., maps and charts), these countries are displayed in grey and labelled accordingly. All core questions required for classification under the monitoring framework were programmed as mandatory. As a result, no key classification variable (e.g., related to Commitment, Action, Accountability) was left unanswered. Internal logical consistency was supported through structured response options and filtering mechanisms. Where a respondent selected "Other" and provided additional qualitative information, this was reviewed and analysed by the project team in line with the definitions embedded in the monitoring framework.

Partial substantive coverage across sections (filtering logic). The monitoring tool is structured around four components: existence of instruments, Commitment, Action, and Accountability. The questionnaire used built-in filtering logic to ensure that (i) countries indicating **no relevant instrument in place** were not presented with the subsequent sections on Commitment, Action, and Accountability, while (ii) countries indicating the existence of at least one relevant instrument were required to complete these sections. As a result, the absence of data in Commitment, Action, or Accountability does not reflect item-level missing data but rather the absence or insufficient scope of instruments at national level.

3.4 DATA ANALYSIS

The analysis focuses on the policy adoption stage and follows the structure of the monitoring framework developed under GenderSAFE. All analytical steps were conducted using the analytical software R for data cleaning, coding, validation, and indicator construction. The analytical strategy was descriptive and based on frequency analysis. Results are presented as absolute counts of participating countries. A total of 18 countries submitted fully completed questionnaires and were included in the dataset.

Indicator construction and classification. Classifications (Comprehensive, Developing, Intermediary, Emerging, Absent) were applied strictly according to the predefined thresholds in the monitoring framework and operational indicator matrix. Each pillar (Commitment, Action, Accountability) was operationalised through a defined set of questionnaire items. Commitment corresponds to section C of the questionnaire, Action was covered in section D, and Accountability is in section E. Countries were classified based on the exact number of required elements fulfilled, in line with the defined cut-offs.

Policy outlook classification. The Policy Outlook indicator (Strengthened, Unchanged, Weakened) was primarily rule-based, relying on structured questionnaire responses. Where respondents selected “Other” and provided additional qualitative explanation, the text was reviewed and classifications were assigned. These open-ended responses were used to clarify planned developments but did not override structured responses unless explicitly warranted.

Analytical scope and reporting approach. All results are reported as absolute counts. The relevant denominators are provided to contextualise the counts. For the overview of instruments and the Policy Outlook indicator, counts are based on all participating countries (N = 18). Bulgaria submitted a questionnaire indicating that no dedicated or general instruments addressing gender-based violence in research and innovation or higher education are currently in place and therefore only responded to questions related to policy outlook. To ensure comparability with the monitoring framework, several relevant general instruments were identified based on previous GenderSAFE and UniSAFE mappings and subsequently confirmed with the national authority. In Chapter 5 National policies: Key Features and EU coordination, counts are based on 17 countries, as Bulgaria did not provide responses to the questions related to policy adoption. For the detailed assessment of the Commitment, Action, and Accountability pillars, an analytical scope rule was applied whereby only countries classified as Comprehensive, Developing, or Intermediary in the instrument overview were included (N = 12). Countries categorised as Emerging or Absent

were excluded from pillar-level analysis because their reported instruments were either general frameworks addressing violence against women or gender equality without specific provisions for research and innovation and higher education or were not sufficiently comprehensive to allow meaningful evaluation against the three pillars of the Zero-Tolerance Code of Conduct. The relevant denominator (N) is indicated beside each figure to aid comparability. No percentages were calculated for the full population of EU Member States or Associated Countries; the report presents counts exclusively for submitted and analysable data. In map visualisations, countries excluded from pillar-level analysis are displayed in a lighter shade of grey and labelled “Not included in analysis,” clearly distinguished from countries that did not submit data, which are shown in a darker grey and labelled “No data.”

Treatment of multiple-response items. For multiple-response questions (such as those capturing types of actions required or recommended by national instruments), results reflect the number of countries that selected each element (absolute counts). This approach ensures that each reported value directly represents the count of countries identifying a given measure within their national framework.

3.5 DATA PRESENTATION AND VISUALISATION

Charts were produced using Microsoft Excel and present absolute counts only, with denominators (N) shown for each figure. For multiple-response items, charts display the frequency of country selections per element. No category collapsing or threshold adjustments were introduced beyond the predefined classification rules.

Geographic visualisations were produced in QGIS for spatial processing and classification, with the Leaflet extension used for interactive outputs. The base geographic layer draws on Eurostat GISCO shapefiles to ensure conformity with official European Commission geographic standards. Only participating countries are colour-coded according to their analytical classification; non-participating countries are displayed in dark grey and labelled “No data.”

The colour scheme was custom-designed in accordance with the GenderSAFE visual identity and reflects the traffic-light logic applied in the monitoring framework (green–yellow–orange–red spectrum in GenderSAFE deliverable D5.1). Two shades of grey were used to clearly distinguish analytical status: countries that did not submit responses are shown in dark grey and labelled “No data,” while countries classified as Emerging or Absent and therefore excluded from pillar-level analysis are shown in a lighter shade of grey and labelled “Not included in analysis.” Map categories strictly follow the classification thresholds defined in the monitoring framework tables in D5.1 and the operational indicator matrix. No additional grouping, smoothing, scaling, or post-hoc adjustments were applied, ensuring full alignment between analytical coding and visual representation.

3.6 LIMITATIONS

The findings of this cross-country analysis should be interpreted considering several limitations.

Incomplete coverage: Not all EU MS and AC contributed to the data collection, so the overview does not fully capture the diversity of national policy landscapes across the ERA.

Self-reported data: The monitoring relies primarily on information provided by national authorities, which may introduce inconsistencies due to differences in interpretation, reporting practices, or internal coordination.

Cross-country heterogeneity: Substantial variability in legal systems, governance structures, and terminology affects comparability, even where similar policy mechanisms exist.

Rapid policy change: The policy environment is evolving quickly, and some frameworks were under revision or pending approval during the data collection period, creating an unavoidable time lag between reported and current developments.

Limited capture of sub-national variation: In federal or devolved systems, the methodology captures national-level provisions more consistently than sub-national differences, which can be significant where regions hold legislative or implementation authority.

To mitigate these limitations, the project team implemented several measures, including multiple rounds of reminders and personalised outreach to national authorities to maximise participation; the development of a detailed glossary, FAQs, and guidance materials to enhance interpretative consistency; the design of a flexible monitoring framework capable of capturing diverse legal and policy configurations and their combinations across governance systems; the application of conservative rule-based coding with targeted verification where needed; and the clear distinction between non-participation (“No data”) and analytical exclusion (“Not included in analysis”) in visualisations.

4. MAIN FINDINGS

This section presents the main findings, pointing to a policy field that has been maturing rapidly in several national contexts, with evidence of progress since 2023 and increasing adoption of sector-specific instruments. Yet it also highlights structural issues: progress is more visible in terms of new instruments adopted and in the articulation of institutional actions required or recommended by the national policies from the obligated institutions, but in some cases without systemic, intersectional framing (Commitment) and, most critically, without enforceable monitoring, reporting and evaluation (Accountability).

POLICY TRAJECTORIES ARE EMERGING

Early starters are moving into policy review and reinforcement, while newer adopters are developing new sector-specific policies and initiatives.

The monitoring reveals distinct trajectories of national policy development. A first group of **early starters** (Ireland, France) has established dedicated sector-specific frameworks and is now moving toward review, renewal, and strengthening. Ireland is revising its 2019 national framework through an expert review and stakeholder consultation process, with implementation of a revised framework planned for 2026; France signals continuation of its 2021–2025 national action plan and preparation of a new roadmap following evaluation.

A second trajectory is visible among **newer adopters, including widening countries (Czechia, Denmark, Poland)**, where sector-specific provisions are becoming more visible through new standards, funded initiatives, and instruments, even if in some instances a dedicated policy framework may still be under development.

A third pattern is observed in countries with **long-standing gender mainstreaming governance frameworks** (Sweden, Iceland), where established gender equality requirements are in place but have not recently been complemented by new policy measures specifically targeting research and innovation and higher education. This suggests that while gender mainstreaming can provide an important framework, it does not ensure further sector-specific policy evolution.

A HETEROGENEOUS LANDSCAPE

Policy mixes are expanding, but dedicated instruments remain limited to a small group of countries.

Across the responding countries, the results confirm that national frameworks addressing gender-based violence in R&I and higher education are highly uneven in both scope and whether they **address specifically the higher education and/or research and innovation** sectors. Only a small set of countries currently combine instruments dedicated to the R&I and higher education sector with a broader national policy or law in a way that produces an overall comprehensive policy mix.

- **Comprehensive** sets of instruments (dedicated policy/law in place): **Belgium, France, Ireland, the Netherlands, Portugal.**
- **Developing** sets of instruments (general policy/law AND a dedicated initiative): **Austria, Czechia, Denmark, Poland.**
- **Intermediary** sets of instruments (general policy/law OR dedicated initiative): **Lithuania, Sweden, Norway.**
- **Emerging** sets of instruments (general national plans on gender-based violence /violence against women without explicitly addressing R&I and higher education): **Croatia, Slovakia, Albania, Iceland.**
- **Absent** sets of instruments (general law on gender equality and/or violence against women): **Bulgaria, Finland.**

A key message is that general legal frameworks (e.g., anti-discrimination, labour law, violence against women, or sexual harassment) are widespread and embedded in EU legislation, but do not automatically translate into policies and actions relevant to R&I and higher education, particularly where students are not covered by labour-based provisions and where institutional responsibilities, procedures, and reporting expectations are not specified for the sector.

INCREASING POLICY ATTENTION

Visible progress has occurred since 2023, with policy layering rather than single-instrument solutions.

Policy attention has increased in recent years, with a significant number of **new instruments and their revisions adopted from 2023 onwards**. This is most visible in countries that have adopted dedicated instruments or expanded sectoral initiatives.

New developments include:

- **Belgium (Flemish):** adoption of a **Decree on Transgressive Behaviour in Higher Education (2023)** and related instruments (including a 2023 circular for prevention and combating harassment, discrimination, and sexual violence in higher education contexts).
- **The Netherlands:** a sustained sequence of measures (**Integral Policy on Social Safety (2023)**, a **Programme (2024–2027)**, and associated instruments including a **Subsidy Scheme (2025–2027)** and a sectoral conference) indicating structured institutionalisation through a multi-year policy approach.
- **Portugal:** adoption of **Law n. 61/2023** addressing harassment and sexual violence in higher education.

Overall, this pattern suggests that progress is currently being made largely through **policy layering and policy mixes**, although a single framework law model is also in evidence.

ALIGNMENT WITH THE ZERO-TOLERANCE CODE OF CONDUCT

Action is more developed than Commitment, while Accountability remains the most systematic gap.

Alignment with the Zero-Tolerance Code of Conduct varies markedly across the three pillars. The pattern emerging from the traffic-light synthesis is consistent across countries: Action measures are more likely to be present and operationalised than Accountability, while Commitment is the weakest pillar overall.

Commitment: no country reaches “comprehensive” or “developing” stage

The Commitment pillar assesses whether national frameworks recognise gender-based violence as systemic and gendered, grounded in the recognition of unequal power relations and intersecting inequalities, and whether they articulate zero-tolerance principles as defined in the Zero-Tolerance Code of Conduct and priority groups. Under the current operationalisation, **no country reaches the “comprehensive” or “developing” commitment categories, making it the weakest pillar.**

Instead:

- **Intermediary commitment** is recorded for eight countries: **Austria, Czechia, France, Ireland, the Netherlands, Portugal, Sweden, Norway.**
- **Absent commitment** is recorded for four countries: **Belgium, Denmark, Lithuania, Poland.**

This finding does not imply a complete lack of national commitment; rather, it highlights that **the explicit framing and conceptual elements emphasised by the Zero-Tolerance Code of Conduct are not consistently codified** in national instruments for R&I and higher education. In some countries, they may be present in the broad laws and policies to counteract gender-based violence or violence against women but are not reflected or operationalised in R&I and higher education instruments.

Action: a substantial number of countries require/recommend multiple institutional actions, but none cover the full breadth

The Action pillar assesses whether national frameworks translate expectations into concrete institutional measures across the UniSAFE 7P framework:

- **No country is classified as “comprehensive”** (i.e., requiring/recommending a range across the full 7P spectrum).
- **Developing action** is recorded for five countries: **Belgium, Denmark, France, Ireland, Portugal.**
- **Intermediary action** is recorded for four countries: **Czechia, Lithuania, the Netherlands, Sweden.**
- **Absent action** is recorded for **Poland and Norway.**

The more detailed thematic breakdown of Action measures points to two additional patterns:

- **Prevention and protection are most frequently addressed**, indicating that many national frameworks address gender-based violence through requirements related to awareness raising, training, communication, and victim- and survivor-support measures.
- **Leadership capacity building is rarely addressed in the national policy frameworks.** Only **France and the Netherlands** are identified as explicitly recommending capacity building for senior and middle leadership roles, while nine countries do not address this dimension.

Accountability: the widest spread across countries

The Accountability pillar assesses whether national frameworks include elements such as monitoring and evaluation, reporting requirements (including budgeting), leadership responsibility, and sanctions/enforcement. The monitoring findings identify accountability as the dimension with the widest spread, with only a limited number of countries reaching comprehensive levels while the majority remain at the lower end of the scale:

- **Comprehensive** accountability mechanisms are recorded for four countries: **Austria, France, Ireland, Sweden.**
- **Emerging** accountability mechanisms are recorded for in six countries: **Czechia, Denmark, the Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Norway.**
- **Absent** accountability mechanisms are recorded for two countries: **Belgium and Lithuania.**

These findings suggest that in many national contexts, institutional action is increasingly encouraged or required, but **system-level oversight and enforceability are not institutionalised**. The accountability framework highlights several elements that remain absent in many cases, including requirements for institutional reporting on actions and budgets, national monitoring with indicators, evaluation mechanisms, explicit senior management accountability, and sanctions for non-compliance. The more detailed accountability section shows that some accountability components do exist in selected countries. For example, senior management responsibility is reported as present in a group of countries, but this does not consistently translate into broader monitoring/evaluation/reporting systems.

STAKEHOLDERS AND DEFINITIONS

Dedicated instruments are associated with broader stakeholder engagement and broader definitions of misconduct.

Where countries have adopted sector-specific instruments, these tend to be characterised by:

- greater involvement of **multiple stakeholder groups** (e.g., other ministries, experts, NGOs, staff organisations/trade unions, student associations and initiatives, umbrella organisations); and

- **broader conceptualisation of the behaviours addressed**, increasingly including transgressive behaviour, abuse of power, intimidation, discrimination and related forms of harm (rather than only sexual harassment narrowly construed).

POLICY OUTLOOK IS STRENGTHENING UNEVENLY

No country reports policy weakening. While policy strengthening is reported in several countries, potential risks relate to institutional capacity, resourcing, and long-term sustainability.

A policy outlook indicator was used to capture whether countries report plans to strengthen, maintain, or weaken their current frameworks.

- **Strengthened outlook** for nine countries: **Austria, Belgium, Croatia, Czechia, France, Ireland, the Netherlands, Portugal, Albania**
- **Unchanged outlook** for eight countries: **Bulgaria, Denmark, Finland, Poland, Slovakia, Sweden, Iceland, Norway**
- **Weakened outlook for no country**

Importantly, the nature of “strengthening” varies:

- **Strengthened legislation and reporting expectations.** The **Netherlands** is highlighted as developing an amendment introducing a formal “duty of care for safety,” including obligations to monitor perceived safety, record incidents, and report serious incidents to the Education Inspectorate.
- **Framework renewal through structured evaluation and revision cycles.** **Ireland** is revising its 2019 framework following expert work and consultations, with implementation planned for 2026; **France** reports continuation of the 2021–2025 plan and preparation of a new roadmap following evaluation, indicating strengthening through review cycles.

At the same time, the comments received suggest that “no weakening” does not mean that risks of policy weakening are inherently absent. Where frameworks rely on fragmented provisions and ad hoc programme funding, vulnerabilities may emerge due to **resourcing and sustainability limitations**, or due to the absence of legal or policy anchoring of the instruments in place to stabilise policy implementation over time.

5. NATIONAL POLICIES: KEY FEATURES AND EU COORDINATION

5.1 COMPREHENSIVENESS OF THE POLICY MIX IN PLACE

Here we review the comprehensiveness of the instruments in place at the national level in line with the indicators in *Table 1*. *Overall comprehensiveness of the national legal and policy framework* in Appendix 1. Operationalisation of the Indicators.

Figure 1. Overview of the Comprehensiveness of the Instruments in Place (N=18)

Countries with a comprehensive set of instruments: Countries that have a dedicated policy or law in place, or both.

5 Countries: *Belgium, France, Ireland, the Netherlands, Portugal*

Countries with a developing set of instruments: Countries that have a more general policy or law in place, as well as a dedicated initiative.

4 Countries: *Austria, Czechia, Denmark, Poland*

Countries with an intermediary set of instruments: Countries that have a more general policy or law in place, or a dedicated initiative is in place.

3 Countries: *Lithuania, Sweden, Norway*

Countries with an emerging set of instruments: Countries that have a general National Action Plan or equivalent policy addressing gender-based violence or violence against women in general, but without specific reference to higher education and/or research.

4 Countries: *Croatia, Slovakia; Albania, Iceland*

Countries with an absent set of instruments: Countries that only have a general law addressing anti-discrimination, gender equality and/or violence against women.

2 Countries: *Bulgaria, Finland*

5.2 NATIONAL POLICY ADOPTION

5.2.1 Public Consultation and Stakeholder Engagement

A majority of countries indicate that their main policy was developed through public consultation. Public consultation is reported in 12 out of 17 countries (Croatia, Czechia, Denmark, France, Ireland, Lithuania, Poland, Slovakia, Sweden, Albania, Iceland, Norway). Four countries report no public consultation (Austria, Belgium, the Netherlands, Portugal). Finland reports “I don’t know.”

Stakeholder engagement is reported even more consistently: 14 out of 17 countries report stakeholder engagement in the drafting stage (Austria, Belgium, Czechia, Denmark, France, Ireland, Lithuania, the Netherlands, Poland, Slovakia, Sweden, Albania, Iceland, Norway), while three report “I don’t know” (Croatia, Finland, Portugal).

Among the 14 countries reporting stakeholder engagement, the most frequently involved stakeholder group is **ministries/government departments** (13/14: all except Lithuania). Expert and sectoral engagement is also common: **researchers/experts on gender-based violence** are reported in 9/14 (Belgium, Czechia, Denmark, Ireland, the Netherlands, Slovakia, Sweden, Albania, Iceland). **Specialised non-governmental organisations** are reported in 8/14 (Albania, Czechia, Denmark, France, Iceland, Ireland, Norway, Slovakia), and **student initiatives and associations** in 8/14 (Belgium, France, Ireland, the Netherlands, Poland, Slovakia, Sweden, Iceland). **Staff organisations/trade unions** are reported in 7/14 (Denmark, France, the Netherlands, Poland, Sweden, Iceland, Norway). By contrast, **survivor groups** are reported in only 2/14 (the Netherlands, Slovakia).

Seven countries provide additional “Other” stakeholder information (Austria, Belgium, Czechia, Denmark, Lithuania, the Netherlands, Norway), typically indicating involvement of higher education and research institutions, umbrella organisations, or research funding organisations. Overall, engagement tends to be **government-led and expert-oriented**, with relatively frequent inclusion of student and staff voices, and limited reported involvement of survivor groups.

5.2.2 Types of Misconduct Covered

Most countries provide concrete terminology used in the main instrument, but the level of specificity varies. 13 countries provide explicit terms or descriptions (Austria, Belgium, Czechia, Denmark, France, Ireland, the Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Sweden, Albania, Iceland, Norway). Two countries do not specify terms (Finland, Lithuania). One country

provides a link only (Slovakia), and one response indicates that there is no dedicated instrument specifically addressing gender-based violence in higher education and research and innovation (Croatia).

Where terms are specified, **the dominant framing remains centred on harassment/sexual harassment** and closely related concepts, often combined with broader references to violence. Examples include explicit references to “sexual harassment/harassment” (e.g., Austria, Czechia, Denmark, Sweden, Iceland, Norway), “sexual misconduct” (Ireland), and “harassment/sexual harassment” combined with violence and discrimination categories (Albania). Several countries use broader “social safety/boundary crossing” frames (e.g., Belgium: “transgressive/boundary-crossing behaviour,” unwanted sexual behaviour and bullying; the Netherlands: (sexual) boundary-crossing behaviour, abuse of power, intimidation, discrimination/racism). France uses a framing centred on “sexist and sexual violence.” Poland notes that the reference instrument frames misconduct in general terms, without enumerating specific types.

Harassment/sexual harassment thus remain a central category, alongside a range of country specific definitions of misconduct, moving toward broader framings that explicitly include abuse of power, intimidation, or discrimination.

5.2.3 Institutional Scope

Coverage is **universal for public higher education institutions**: all 17 countries report that the main instrument applies to them. Beyond this, coverage is more uneven:

- Private/non-public higher education institutions: 12/17 (Croatia, Czechia, Denmark, Finland, France, Lithuania, Poland, Portugal, Slovakia, Sweden, Iceland, Norway)
- Public-private higher education institutions: 13/17 (Austria, Croatia, Czechia, Denmark, Finland, France, Lithuania, Poland, Portugal, Slovakia, Albania, Iceland, Norway)
- Public research institutions: 12/17 (Austria, Croatia, Denmark, Finland, France, Lithuania, Poland, Slovakia, Sweden, Albania, Iceland, Norway)
- Private research institutions: 8/17 (Croatia, Denmark, Finland, France, Lithuania, Slovakia, Sweden, Norway)
- Public research funding organisations: 9/17 (Austria, Croatia, Denmark, Finland, Lithuania, Slovakia, Albania, Iceland, Norway)
- Private research funding organisations: 6/17 (Croatia, Denmark, Finland, Lithuania, Slovakia, Albania)
- Public administration bodies: 9/17 (Austria, Croatia, Denmark, Finland, Lithuania, Slovakia, Albania, Iceland, Norway)

Overall, national instruments most consistently cover higher education, while coverage becomes more selective for research institutions (especially private research institutions) and for research funding organisations, which has implications for coverage across the research career path and mobility across organisational types.

5.2.4 Budget Allocation for Policy Implementation

A dedicated implementation budget is reported in 9/17 countries (Czechia, Denmark, France, Ireland, Lithuania, the Netherlands, Poland, Slovakia, Albania). Four report no budget (Austria, Belgium, Sweden, Iceland), and four report “I don’t know” (Croatia, Finland, Portugal, Norway).

Where a budget exists (9 countries), the most common form is a **central government budget** line (6/9: Denmark, France, Ireland, Poland, Slovakia, Albania), while **time-limited programme/project funding** is reported in 3/9 (Czechia, Lithuania, the Netherlands). In terms of timeframe, annual recurring allocations are reported in 5/9 (Czechia, France, Ireland, Poland, Albania), multi-annual allocations in 2/9 (Denmark, Lithuania), and “Other” in 2/9 (the Netherlands, Slovakia), with the Netherlands specifying a multi-year budget (16 million euros over 2024–2027).

Budget volumes are frequently not available or not reported as a precise figure: 5/9 indicate that information is not available (Czechia, Denmark, Poland, Slovakia, Albania), while 4/9 provide indicative figures (France, Ireland, Lithuania, the Netherlands). This pattern reinforces the broader finding that resourcing information is often partial, even where a dedicated budget is reported.

5.2.5 Financial Resources to Institutions Covered by the Policy Instrument

Six out of 17 countries report that the reference instrument provides for making financial resources available to obliged institutions (Czechia, France, Ireland, Lithuania, the Netherlands, Slovakia). Four report none (Austria, Belgium, Denmark, Iceland). A further six report “I don’t know” (Croatia, Finland, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Sweden), and Albania selects “Other” (linked to broader strategy implementation). This suggests that even when implementation budgets exist at system level, this does not mean the provision of funding for the institutions covered by the policy. Moreover, information on institutional funding is often not readily available to respondents.

5.3 NATIONAL AND EU POLICY ALIGNMENT

Across the responding countries, **explicit endorsement of the Zero-Tolerance Code of Conduct is limited at this stage**. In a large majority of cases, this is because the national instrument predates 2024 when the Code was adopted: 10 countries reported that endorsement was therefore not applicable (Belgium, Croatia, Denmark, Finland, France, Ireland, Lithuania, the Netherlands, Portugal, and Albania). Overall, this suggests that the Code of Conduct is currently more likely to function as a **reference point for alignment and future revision** than as a framework already embedded in national instruments.

At the same time, most respondents indicated that their main instrument is **aligned with other national policies**, signalling that gender-based violence policies in R&I and higher education, if they exist, typically sit within broader national policy mixes (e.g., equality, labour, education, violence prevention). 16 countries reported full alignment and one partial alignment, noting links mainly to general labour provisions. This widespread alignment provides a basis for coherent implementation, but it also implies that strengthening

alignment with the Code of Conduct may require **integration into existing policy instruments when they are being reviewed**, rather than creating stand-alone instruments.

As regards **coordination of national policies with recent EU developments**, 13 countries stated that their policy instrument was already in place prior to the Ljubljana Declaration, the Gender Equality Plan eligibility criterion, and the ERA Policy Agenda 2022–2024. Where countries did link national developments to EU-level drivers, the most visible catalyst was the **Gender Equality Plan eligibility criterion in Horizon Europe** (selected by Austria, Czechia, and Lithuania). No country reported launching its main policy instrument in direct relation to the adoption of the Zero-Tolerance Code of Conduct, consistent with the Code's recent adoption. This reinforces the importance of further integration of the Code's recommendations through revision of the current policy and legal frameworks.

5.4 POLICY OUTLOOK

The policy outlook is characterised by **selective strengthening** through revisions, governance reinforcement, initiatives, and implementation supports in **Austria, Belgium, Croatia, Czechia, France, Ireland, the Netherlands, Portugal, and Albania**, alongside eight countries reporting **no current strengthening plans** or **weakening** of existing national policy mix: **Bulgaria, Denmark, Finland, Poland, Slovakia, Sweden; Iceland, and Norway**. **Lithuania** stated that it does not have the relevant information available and is therefore unable to provide a definitive response.

Figure 2. Policy Outlook (N=18)

The planned policy advances include:

- Advance provisions in an existing general policy: 4 countries (Croatia, Czechia, Ireland, Albania)
- Advance provisions in an existing dedicated policy: 2 countries (France, Portugal)
- Introduce a new initiative: 2 countries (Austria, Belgium)
- Renew an existing initiative: 1 country (Belgium)
- Adopt a new dedicated policy: 1 country (Austria)
- Amend a general law: 1 country (the Netherlands)

A legal amendment: the Netherlands

The Netherlands is developing an amendment to the Higher Education and Scientific Research Act introducing a **duty of care for safety**, including obligations such as monitoring perceived safety, recording incidents, and reporting serious incidents to the inspectorate.

Framework revision mechanism: Ireland and France

France plans to continue its national policy on Ending Sexual Violence and Harassment beyond the 2021–2025 framework. An Expert Group was convened, consultations were conducted with stakeholders, and implementation of a revised framework is planned for 2026.

Ireland is reviewing and renewing the 2019 national framework through an expert group process and broad consultation, with a revised framework planned for implementation in 2026.

New initiatives or working groups: Austria and Belgium

Austria plans to establish a stakeholder working group to implement the findings and recommendations from the Austrian Action Plan for the European Research Area (ERA-NAP) status quo survey.

Belgium refers to regional action plans, though details are limited. These represent softer governance instruments, based on coordination rather than legal change.

Gender Equality Plan requirement as a driver: Croatia, Slovakia

Croatia highlights mandatory Gender Equality Plans for higher education and research institutions and links gender integration to project eligibility in research funding since 2022. This mechanism embeds gender-based violence prevention within research governance and funding conditionality.

Slovakia reports continuation of Gender Equality Plans, specialised training, internal zero-tolerance policies, and preparation of a draft national strategy for gender equality in research and innovation.

Strategic alignment without specified instruments

Albania frames strengthening within its National Strategy for Gender Equality 2021–2030 and emphasises alignment with EU-level expectations.

6. ZERO-TOLERANCE INDICATORS

The Zero-Tolerance Code of Conduct defines two Commitment recommendations, eight Action recommendations and nine Accountability recommendations. Here we synthesise the results for the countries included in the pillar analysis (N=12), based on the predefined coding specified in *Table 3. Commitment*, *Table 4. Action*, and *Table 5. Accountability* in Appendix 1. Operationalisation of the Indicators.

6.1 OVERVIEW OF INDICATORS

6.1.1 Adoption Indicators

The number of European countries that have adopted a dedicated law and/or policy to address gender-based violence in higher education and/or research and innovation	5	BE FR IE NL PT
The number of European countries that have adopted a more general law and/or policy that encompass addressing gender-based violence in higher education and/or research and innovation	6	AT CZ DK PL SE NO
The number of European countries that have explicitly endorsed the Zero-tolerance code of conduct or some of its principles in their laws/policies/initiatives on gender-based violence in higher education and research.	0	
The number of European countries that allocate a budget to implement laws/policies/initiatives against gender-based violence in higher education and/or research and innovation	9	CZ DK FR IE LT NL PL SK AL

6.1.2 Commitment Indicators

The number of European countries that recognise the systemic nature of gender-based violence in their laws/policies to address gender-based violence	7	AT CZ FR NL PT SE NO
The number of European countries that promote trauma-informed approaches in their laws/policies to address gender-based violence	2	PT SE
The number of European countries that promote victim/survivor-centred approaches in their laws/policies to address gender-based violence.	2	PT SE

The number of European countries that recognise the intersectional nature of gender-based violence in their laws/policies to address gender-based violence.	3	CZ SE NO
The number of European countries whose laws/policies contain provisions targeting specific priority groups (e.g., LGBTQIA+, ethnic minorities, individuals with disabilities, early-career researchers etc.).	5	AT CZ IE NL NO

6.1.3 Action Indicators

Comprehensive policies: The number of European countries that require or recommend that the institutions covered by the laws/policies adopt comprehensive policies to address gender-based violence	5	BE DK IE LT PT
The number of European countries whose laws/policies embed the issue of gender-based violence in higher education and/or research and innovation within institutional change (such as through Gender Equality Plans).	5	CZ FR NL PT SE
Monitoring requirement: The number of European countries that require or recommend that the institutions covered by the laws/policies monitor their policies to address gender-based violence.	3	DK LT PT
Evaluation requirement: The number of European countries that require or recommend that the institutions covered by the laws/policies evaluate the effectiveness of their policies to address gender-based violence.	0	
The number of European countries that require or recommend that the institutions covered by the laws/policies conduct preventive training sessions for staff .	5	BE CZ IE LT SE
The number of European countries that require or recommend that the institutions covered by the laws/policies conduct preventive training sessions for students if relevant.	4	IE LT NL SE

The number of European countries that require or recommend that the institutions covered by the laws/policies conduct capacity building sessions for senior management of higher education and/or research institutions.	1	FR
The number of European countries that require or recommend that the institutions covered by the laws/policies conduct capacity building sessions for staff members in managerial and supervisory positions in higher education and/or research institutions.	2	FR, NL
The number of European countries that require or recommend that the institutions covered by the laws/policies conduct capacity building sessions for staff responsible for case handling .	5	BE CZ FR IE SE
The number of European countries that require or recommend that the institutions covered by the laws/policies conduct active bystander intervention training .	0	
Prevalence and/or incidence data collection: The number of European countries that require or recommend that the institutions covered by the laws/policies collect gender-disaggregated prevalence and/or incidence data at the institutional level.	2	BE, FR
Awareness raising campaigns: The number of European countries that require or recommend that the institutions covered by the laws/policies conduct awareness-raising campaigns (e.g. about unacceptable behaviours and reporting mechanisms).	3	IE, LT, PT
Reporting mechanisms: The number of European countries that require or recommend that the institutions covered by the laws/policies to have reporting mechanisms in place.	7	BE CZ DK FR IE NL PT
Partnerships: The number of European countries that require or recommend that the institutions covered by the laws/policies engage in partnerships with internal and/or external stakeholders.	5	CZ FR NL IE PT

6.1.4 Accountability Indicators

The number of European countries whose national/regional laws/policies ascribe responsibility to institutional senior management (such as presidents, rectors and, at the lower level, deans) for the implementation of institutional policies.	6	AT FR IE NL PL SE
The number of European countries with sanctions in place for the institutions covered by the national/regional laws/policies that are in breach of the law/policy .	5	AT FR IE PL SE
The number of European countries that have put in place concrete measures to prevent multi-site serial misconduct by perpetrators at different institutions.	1	AT
The number of European countries that monitor the implementation of their national/regional laws/policies to counteract gender-based violence in higher education and/or research and innovation.	4	AT FR IE SE
The number of European countries that evaluate the effectiveness of their national/regional laws/policies to counteract gender-based violence in higher education and/or research and innovation.	5	DK IE NL SE NO

6.2 COMMITMENT

The Commitment pillar captures whether national frameworks (i) explicitly recognise gender-based violence as systemic (including unequal power relations in R&I and higher education, existence of violence along a continuum, the need to embed efforts to counteract gender-based violence in institutional change approaches, and recognition of the intersectional nature of gender-based violence), (ii) articulate priority groups, and (iii) explicitly address the defined zero-tolerance principles.

The indicator synthesis identifies Commitment as the weakest pillar. Under the current operationalisation, no country reaches the “comprehensive” or “developing” categories for Commitment; eight countries are classified as “intermediary” (Austria, Czechia, France, Ireland, the Netherlands, Portugal, Sweden, and Norway) and four are classified as “absent” (Belgium, Denmark, Lithuania, and Poland).

This pattern suggests that, even where policy measures exist, the explicit conceptual framing promoted by the Zero-Tolerance Code of Conduct is not consistently embedded in

national instruments. In practice, this means that institutions may receive expectations to act, but without a clearly articulated theoretical and conceptual framing of gender-based violence.

Figure 3. Comprehensiveness of the Commitment Pillar (N=12)

Countries with a comprehensive commitment approach: Countries that fully recognise the systemic, intersectional, and institution-wide nature of gender-based violence and embed multiple zero-tolerance principles and priority groups in their main policy.

0 Countries

Countries with a developing commitment approach: Countries that recognise several core elements of the systemic nature of gender-based violence and articulate a growing set of priority groups and zero-tolerance principles, though not yet comprehensively.

0 Countries

Countries with an intermediary commitment approach: Countries that show a partial or uneven understanding of gender-based violence as a systemic issue and include only some priority groups or zero-tolerance principles in their policy framework.

8 Countries: Austria, Czechia, France, Ireland, the Netherlands, Portugal, Sweden, Norway

Countries with an emerging commitment approach: Countries that acknowledge only limited aspects of gender-based violence as a systemic issue and include minimal references to priority groups or zero-tolerance principles.

0 Countries

Countries with an absent commitment approach: Countries that do not recognise gender-based violence as a systemic issue, do not define priority groups and do not incorporate zero-tolerance principles in their national policy.

4 Countries: Belgium, Denmark, Lithuania, Poland

6.2.1 Recognition of the Systemic Nature of Gender-based Violence

Explicit recognition of the systemic nature of gender-based violence is present in a majority of the analysed countries. **Seven countries (Austria, Czechia, France, the Netherlands, Portugal, Sweden, and Norway) explicitly recognise the systemic nature of gender-based violence** in their instruments, while five (Belgium, Denmark, Ireland, Lithuania, and Poland) do not make this framing explicit.

Among the seven countries that do recognise the systemic nature (Figure 4. Specific Aspects of the Systemic Nature of gender-based violence (N=7)), the most common element is recognition of **unequal power relations in higher education and/or research and innovation** (6/7: Austria, Czechia, France, the Netherlands, Sweden, Norway). A second element is the view that responses should be **embedded in institutional change approaches** (5/7: Czechia, France, the Netherlands, Portugal, Sweden). By contrast, explicit recognition of the **intersectional nature** of gender-based violence (3/7: Czechia, Sweden, Norway) and recognition of violence along a **continuum** (3/7: Czechia, France, Sweden) are less consistently embedded. Czechia and Sweden are the only countries that reference **all four** systemic aspects, while others reference a more selective subset (e.g., Austria only unequal power relations; Portugal only institutional change embedding).

This indicates that, even where policy measures exist, the underlying conceptualisation promoted by the Zero-Tolerance Code of Conduct is not consistently embedded in national policy design, which may in turn shape how comprehensively institutions are expected to address the continuum of behaviours and the organisational conditions that enable gender-based violence.

Figure 4. Specific Aspects of the Systemic Nature of gender-based violence (N=7)

6.2.2 Definition of Priority Groups

Explicit definition of priority groups in national instruments remains limited. Only **five countries (Austria, Czechia, Ireland, the Netherlands, and Norway) explicitly define priority groups** in their instruments, while seven countries (Belgium, Denmark, France, Lithuania, Poland, Portugal, and Sweden) do not.

Among the five countries that do define priority groups (Figure 5. Specific Priority Groups (N=5)), the most commonly recognised groups are **people with disabilities** and **sexual orientation minorities**, both referenced by all five countries. **Ethnic and racial minority groups** are identified in three countries (Austria, Ireland, and Norway), while **precarious employment** is recognised in two (the Netherlands and Norway). A small number of additional groups are mentioned only once each: **socioeconomic status** (Norway), **migration status** (Czechia), **religion** (Czechia), **certain age groups** (the Netherlands), and **mobile students** (Ireland). Notably, several groups often highlighted in intersectional approaches to gender-based violence in R&I and higher education (such as gender identity and gender expression, sex characteristics (intersex), pregnancy/parenthood or caregiver status, chronic illness, neurodiversity, and mobile staff) are not explicitly referenced in the reported instruments of these five countries.

Overall, this suggests that even where priority groups are defined, the operationalisation of intersectionality remains **selective and uneven**, which may shape how effectively national frameworks anticipate differentiated risks, barriers to reporting, and access to support and protection in institutional responses to gender-based violence.

Figure 5. Specific Priority Groups (N=5)

6.2.3 Zero-Tolerance Definitional Elements

The Zero-Tolerance Code of Conduct defines the following elements at its centre:

- Victim-centred or victim-/survivor-centred approach
- Trauma-informed approach
- Whole-institution approach
- Adoption of a zero-tolerance approach
- Commitment to taking all forms of gender-based violence seriously
- Commitment to investigating all reports of gender-based violence incidents.

An explicit statement of these zero-tolerance definitional elements in the national instruments remains limited. **Only four countries (France, the Netherlands, Portugal, and Sweden) explicitly mention the zero-tolerance elements** in their instruments, while eight countries (Austria, Belgium, Czechia, Denmark, Ireland, Lithuania, Poland, and Norway) do not.

Among the four countries that define zero-tolerance elements (Figure 6. Specific Zero-Tolerance Principles (N=4)), the **only one included by all four** is a **whole-institution approach** (France, the Netherlands, Portugal, and Sweden). Furthermore, France and Sweden explicitly include (i) **adoption of a zero-tolerance approach**, (ii) **commitment to taking all forms of gender-based violence seriously**, and (iii) **commitment to investigating all reports**. Portugal and Sweden explicitly include **victim-/survivor-centred** and **trauma-informed** principles. Sweden is the only country that includes **all** the

listed elements, while the Netherlands includes only the whole-institution approach, and France and Portugal each include different subsets.

Figure 6. Specific Zero-Tolerance Principles (N=4)

6.3 ACTION

The Action pillar assesses whether national frameworks require and/or recommend institutional measures across the breadth of the UniSAFE 7P framework. The indicator synthesis indicates that Action is more developed than Commitment but still falls short of the elements recommended in the Zero-Tolerance Code of Conduct. No country is classified as “comprehensive.” Five countries are classified as “developing” (Belgium, Denmark, France, Ireland, and Portugal), four as “intermediary” (Czechia, Lithuania, the Netherlands, and Sweden), one as “emerging” (Austria), and two as “absent” (Poland and Norway).

A key pattern behind these aggregate classifications is that national instruments most often focus on **preventative and protective expectations** (e.g., institutional policy requirements and protective measures), while others remain weakly specified. In particular, expectations on leadership capacity building are rare, and partnership arrangements are uneven. This reinforces the broader finding that many national frameworks increasingly encourage institutional action, but do not yet consistently require a *full-spectrum*, whole-system response aligned with the 7P framework.

Figure 7. Comprehensiveness of the Action Pillar (N=12)

Countries with a comprehensive set of actions: Countries that have national frameworks that require and/or recommend a wide and robust range of institutional actions across the full 7P spectrum, with at least eight action areas mandated or encouraged.

0 Countries

Countries with a developing set of actions: Countries that have frameworks that require and/or recommend a substantial set of institutional actions, covering at least six areas of the 7P model but not yet the full breadth expected under the Zero-Tolerance Code of Conduct.

5 Countries: *Belgium, Denmark, France, Ireland, Portugal*

Countries with an intermediary set of actions: Countries that require and/or recommend a moderate number of institutional actions, encompassing at least four areas of the 7P framework and showing partial operationalisation of the zero-tolerance approach.

4 Countries: *Czechia, Lithuania, the Netherlands, Sweden*

Countries with an emerging set of actions: Countries that mandate or recommend only a limited number of institutional actions, with at least two areas of the 7P model covered, indicating early-stage or fragmented implementation.

1 Country: *Austria*

Countries with an absent set of actions: Countries that do not require or recommend any institutional actions across the 7P areas, demonstrating no operationalisation of the action elements of the Zero-Tolerance Code.

2 Countries: *Poland; Norway*

6.3.1 Institutional Policy

Figure 8 Any Action Required in Relation to Institutional Policy (N=11)

Countries that explicitly **require** actions to be taken by obliged institutions in relation to their own institutional policy.

10 countries: *Belgium, Czechia, Denmark, France, Ireland, Lithuania, the Netherlands, Portugal, Sweden; Norway*

Countries that do not address institutional-level actions in relation to their own institutional policy in their instruments.

1 country: *Austria*

Explicit requirements for institutional-level action in relation to internal institutional policies are present in the majority of national instruments. **10 countries (Belgium, Czechia, Denmark, France, Ireland, Lithuania, the Netherlands, Portugal, Sweden, and Norway)** explicitly require obliged institutions to take some action. In contrast, one country (Austria) does not address institutional-level actions related to internal policy in its national instrument.

Among the 10 countries that explicitly require institutional-level action (Figure 9. Specific Actions Required in Relation to Institutional Policy (N=10) , the most common requirement is **the adoption of an institutional policy** (Belgium, Denmark, Ireland, Lithuania, and Portugal). A slightly narrower group (Denmark, Lithuania, and Portugal) also **requires institutions to monitor the implementation of their institutional policy**. The **establishment of a contact point** is mandated in three countries (Belgium, Czechia, and

Sweden). None of the countries explicitly require the **definition of monitoring indicators** or **the evaluation of the effectiveness** of the institutional policy.

The responses under “**Other**” provide further specification of the existing requirements and list other additional measures too. In addition to creating independent contact points for students and staff with reporting obligations to management, **Belgium** refers to establishing a behavioural code jointly developed by university management and student representatives and setting up a complaints registry. Confirming the need to embed efforts to counteract gender-based violence in the institutional change approach, **France** requires the adoption of a Gender Equality Plan covering discrimination, violence, and harassment, and obliges public employers to establish a dedicated service to support victims of sexual violence. **Lithuania** requires employers with more than fifty employees to adopt and implement a formal policy on the prevention of violence and harassment, including definitions, reporting and examination procedures, protection and assistance measures for victims and whistleblowers, and clear rules on employee conduct. **The Netherlands** highlights the requirement to adopt a code of conduct. **Portugal** emphasises the establishment of psychological and therapeutic support services. **Norway** states that universities and university colleges must actively work to prevent and stop harassment and ensure access to a student ombud.

Figure 9. Specific Actions Required in Relation to Institutional Policy (N=10)

6.3.2 Prevalence/Incidence Data

Figure 10. Prevalence/Incidence Data (N=11)

Countries whose instruments explicitly **require** establishing prevalence or incidence at the institutional level.

4 countries: *Belgium, Denmark, Ireland, the Netherlands*

Countries whose instruments explicitly **recommend** establishing prevalence or incidence at the institutional level.

3 countries: *Czechia, France, Portugal*

Countries that **do not address** establishing prevalence or incidence at the institutional level in their instruments.

4 countries: *Austria, Lithuania, Sweden; Norway*

Across the countries included in the Action analysis (N=11), requirements to establish institutional-level prevalence/incidence are present but not yet universal. Four countries explicitly require this (Belgium, Denmark, Ireland, the Netherlands), three countries recommend it (Czechia, France, Portugal), and four countries do not address it in their instruments (Austria, Lithuania, Sweden, Norway).

Among the seven countries that require or recommend establishing prevalence/incidence (Belgium, Denmark, Ireland, the Netherlands, Czechia, France, Portugal), the most common specification is administrative data collection, centralisation, and analysis (4/7: Belgium, France, Ireland, Portugal). This is followed by other types of surveys that include questions on gender-based violence (3/7: Denmark, France, the Netherlands). Two countries mention gender-disaggregated data collection and monitoring of disciplinary and grievance procedures (Belgium, France) and institution-wide prevalence studies/surveys (Denmark, France). Only one country explicitly references online reporting data analysis (Denmark). Only one country explicitly references online reporting data analysis (Denmark).

Figure 11. Specific Types of Prevalence/Incidence Data (N=7)

Denmark has provided additional information related to reporting to the national authority. While institutions are legally required to prevent and address harassment and sexism, there is no obligation to systematically report prevalence or incidence data externally to the government. Universities must ensure a safe psychological learning environment under the Educational Environment Act and are obliged to manage harassment cases internally, including sexual harassment as defined in the Gender Equality Act. A national anti-harassment policy agreed between the Ministry of Higher Education and universities, as well as sector frameworks, requires institutions to establish clear internal reporting procedures, safe complaint channels, and whistleblower systems, often allowing anonymous reporting. However, there is no automatic or centralised national reporting system for individual incidents, and external reporting of all cases is not mandatory.

6.3.3 Preventive Actions

Figure 12. Preventive Actions (N=11)

Countries whose instruments explicitly **require** preventive actions to address gender-based violence to be taken by the obliged institution:

7 countries: *Austria, Belgium, Czechia, France, Ireland, Lithuania, Sweden*

Countries whose instruments explicitly **recommend** preventive actions to address gender-based violence to be taken by the obliged institution:

2 countries: *the Netherlands, Portugal*

Countries that **do not address** preventive actions to address gender-based violence in their instruments:

2 countries: *Denmark; Norway*

Across the countries included in the Action analysis (N=11), preventive actions to address gender-based violence are widely covered: seven countries explicitly require preventive actions (Austria, Belgium, Czechia, France, Ireland, Lithuania, Sweden), two recommend them (the Netherlands, Portugal), and two do not address preventive actions in their instruments (Denmark, Norway).

Looking at the type of preventive actions specified (N=9 countries that require/recommend prevention), the most frequently named measures are awareness raising (3/9: Ireland, Lithuania, Portugal) and continuous staff training (3/9: Czechia, Ireland, Sweden). A smaller subset specifies mandatory induction training for staff (2/9: Belgium, Lithuania), voluntary induction training for students (2/9: Ireland, the Netherlands), and continuous student training (2/9: Ireland, Sweden). Only Sweden explicitly references proactive risk assessment (1/9) and integration of gender-based violence into curricula, research ethics, and training programmes (1/9). Notably, none of the countries explicitly select communication campaigns, active bystander training, or safe and inclusive campus design as specified preventive actions.

Figure 13. Specific Protective Actions (N=9)

The responses under **Other** indicate varying degrees of specificity in preventive requirements across countries. **Austria** states that the Federal Equal Opportunities Act obliges institutions to take appropriate preventive measures but leaves the choice and design of specific actions to institutional discretion. **Belgium** clarifies that mandatory training applies only to designated contact points rather than to the broader institutional community. The **Netherlands** refers to the establishment of codes of conduct and a legal amendment to the Higher Education and Scientific Research Act reinforcing institutional responsibility for social safety. **Sweden**, through its ordinance and the Discrimination Act, requires institutions to have clear guidelines, protocols, and procedures to prevent and address harassment and sexual harassment affecting both students and staff.

6.3.4 Capacity Building

Figure 14. Capacity Building (N=11)

Countries whose instruments explicitly **recommend** capacity building for those in senior and middle leadership roles:

2 countries: *France, the Netherlands*

Countries that do not address capacity building for those in senior and middle leadership roles in their instruments:

9 countries: *Austria, Belgium, Czechia, Denmark, Ireland, Lithuania, Portugal, Sweden, Norway*

Capacity building for those in senior and middle leadership roles is rarely specified at system level. No country explicitly requires such capacity building. Only two countries recommend it (France and the Netherlands), while nine countries do not address leadership capacity building in their instruments at all (Austria, Belgium, Czechia, Denmark, Ireland, Lithuania, Portugal, Sweden, Norway).

Among the two countries that recommend leadership capacity building, the emphasis is uneven. Both include staff in supervisory roles, but France additionally covers senior management (e.g., rectors, deans, directors) and middle management (e.g., heads of department, group leaders), and notes “PhD supervisors” under “Other.” The Netherlands, by contrast, indicates capacity building only for staff in supervisory roles, without explicitly covering senior or middle management categories in the response options.

Taken together, this is a notable implementation gap. While many instruments require or recommend institutional preventative measures, far fewer make explicit the expectation that those with decision-making power and management responsibility should receive targeted capacity building. This may contribute to uneven institutional practice, particularly where leadership roles are central to setting standards, ensuring procedural quality, and preventing retaliation.

Figure 15. Specific Capacity Building (N=2)

6.3.5 Protective Actions

Figure 16. Protective Actions (N=11)

Countries whose instruments explicitly require protective actions to be taken by the obliged institutions:

8 countries: *Austria, Belgium, Denmark, France, Ireland, Lithuania, the Netherlands, Sweden*

Countries whose instruments explicitly recommend protective actions to be taken by the obliged institutions:

2 countries: *Czechia, Portugal*

Countries that do not address protective actions to be taken by the obliged institutions in their instruments:

1 country: Norway

Eight countries explicitly require protective actions (Austria, Belgium, Denmark, France, Ireland, Lithuania, the Netherlands, Sweden), two recommend them (Czechia, Portugal), and one country does not address protective actions in its instruments (Norway).

Among the 10 countries that require or recommend protective actions, the most frequently specified measures relate to **reporting, complaint infrastructure, and procedural capacity**. The most common element is a **contact point or staff member to receive reports** (7/10: Austria, Czechia, Denmark, France, Ireland, Portugal, Sweden). This is followed by **non-anonymous formal complaint channels** (6/10: Austria, Belgium, Denmark, France, Ireland, Sweden) and **training for staff responsible for case management** (5/10: Belgium, Czechia, France, Ireland, Sweden). **Non-anonymous informal complaint channels** are specified by four countries (Austria, Belgium, Denmark, Sweden), while **anonymous reporting channels** are specified by three (Belgium, Denmark, Sweden). **Precautionary measures** are also specified by three (Austria, France, Sweden).

By contrast, measures that reflect **more individualised protection and longer-term safeguarding** are less consistently specified. **Risk assessments and safety planning** appear in two countries (France, Sweden), as do **confidentiality safeguards** (Austria, Sweden) and protection against retaliation (Austria, Sweden). Only Sweden explicitly specifies **follow-up and case monitoring**, and no country specifies access to safe spaces or temporary housing. Lithuania is coded as “not specified” in terms of which protective actions are included, despite indicating that protective actions are required.

The responses under “**Other**” highlight different approaches to protective measures. **Czechia** refers to its Action Plan, which foresees the development of a methodological document for universities outlining recommended procedures in cases of gender-based violence, including sexual harassment and abuse, and regulating the role and activities of ombuds services in this area. The **Netherlands** reports the initiation of an investigation into the quality of institutional complaint channels, with a view to improving them, including consideration of whether anonymous reporting mechanisms should be introduced.

Overall, the pattern suggests that system-level protective expectations most often prioritise accessible reporting/complaint channels and procedural guidance, while more comprehensive protection elements (tailored safety planning, anti-retaliation safeguards, sustained follow-up) are less consistently embedded.

Figure 17. Specific Protective Actions (N=10)

6.3.6 Investigative/Disciplinary Actions

Figure 18. Investigative/Disciplinary Actions (N=11)

Countries whose instruments explicitly require the introduction of investigative and/or disciplinary actions:

5 countries: *Austria, Denmark, France, Lithuania, Sweden*

Countries whose instruments explicitly recommend the introduction of investigative and/or disciplinary actions:

2 countries: *Belgium, Ireland*

Countries that do not address the introduction of investigative and/or disciplinary actions in their instruments:

4 countries: *Czechia, Netherlands, Portugal; Norway*

Explicit requirements on **investigative and/or disciplinary actions** are present in a majority, but are not universal: five countries require (**Austria, Denmark, France, Lithuania, Sweden**), two recommend (**Belgium, Ireland**) and four **do not** address this element (**Czechia, the Netherlands, Portugal, Norway**).

Compared with prevention and protection, investigative/disciplinary elements are more unevenly specified at system level. A sizeable minority of national frameworks appear to leave investigative and disciplinary design to institutional autonomy and/or to broader labour/administrative frameworks, rather than setting explicit sector-level expectations.

Among the **seven** countries that **require or recommend** investigative/disciplinary actions, the most common elements are:

- Define disciplinary measures and sanctions (4/7): Austria, Denmark, France, Sweden
- Define an investigative procedure (principles + committee set-up) (3/7): Denmark, France, Sweden
- Open communication on investigation outcomes (1/7): France
- Open communication on disciplinary actions/sanctions given (1/7): France

The results show that where instruments do address investigation/discipline, they most often prioritise **procedural definition and sanctions** (how investigations and disciplinary measures should be set up), while **transparency elements** (communication about outcomes or sanctions) are rarely explicit.

The responses under “**Other**” show different levels of regulatory detail regarding investigative and disciplinary procedures. **Belgium** indicates that the legal framework does not define specific measures or sanctions; it only allows contact points to alert the disciplinary commission or the police in cases of “acute risk,” such as danger to life or serious aggression. Suspension is possible only if the institution initiates a formal investigation, meaning that disciplinary consequences depend on internal procedures rather than predefined sanctions in the instrument itself. **Ireland**, by contrast, reports that administrative data is collected on completed investigations each academic year and that the national Framework requires institutions to ensure robust reporting and investigation

procedures. While no standalone outcome focuses exclusively on investigations, institutions are expected to operate systems compatible with complainant and survivor rights, adopt trauma-informed approaches in handling reports and investigations, and collaborate with external stakeholders, including organisations working on sexual violence.

Figure 19. Specific Investigative/Disciplinary Actions (N=7)

6.3.7 Provision of Services

Figure 20. Provision of Service (N=11)

Countries whose instruments explicitly require actions to be taken by obliged institutions in relation to the provision of services:

5 countries: *Denmark, France, Ireland, Portugal, Sweden*

Countries whose instruments explicitly recommend actions to be taken by obliged institutions in relation to the provision of services:

2 countries: *Belgium, Czechia*

Countries that do not address actions related to the provision of services in their instruments:

4 countries: *Austria, Lithuania, the Netherlands; Norway*

Among the seven countries that **require or recommend** action on services (**Belgium, Czechia, Denmark, France, Ireland, Portugal, Sweden**), the monitoring shows **limited specification** of concrete service types in most cases, with one country (Sweden) standing out as the most comprehensive.

Most frequently specified options are **psychological and therapeutic services in Denmark, Portugal, and Sweden; crisis intervention services in Denmark and Sweden; and academic or workplace accommodations (e.g., extensions, changes in supervision, relocation) in France and Sweden**. Other services are reported only by individual countries: **legal advice and support in Denmark; medical care, sexual and reproductive health services, and medical referrals in Sweden**.

Under “Other”, **Belgium** states that their instrument lists five possible actions for a confidentiality officer: active listening conversations, mediation with the agreement of all parties involved, reporting or intervention within the institution with the explicit consent of the reporter, targeted referral, and identifying and supporting additional internal or external actions if initial measures are considered insufficient. **France** indicates that the General Public Service Code requires a reporting mechanism including procedures to receive reports, to refer victims to appropriate support services and professionals, and to direct victims or witnesses to competent authorities for protection and administrative investigation. **Ireland** refers to a Framework requirement that higher education institutions provide accessible, trauma-informed services to support student disclosure, reporting, and complaints, as well as counselling and advocacy.

Figure 21. Specific Service Provided (N=8)

6.3.8 Partnership

Figure 22. Partnership (N=11)

Countries whose instruments explicitly require partnerships between the obligated organisations and other institutions:

1 country: Ireland

Countries whose instruments explicitly recommend partnerships between the obligated organisations and other institutions:

4 countries: Czechia, France, the Netherlands, Portugal

Countries that do not address partnerships in their instruments:

6 countries: Austria, Belgium, Denmark, Lithuania, Sweden; Norway

Across the 11 countries included in the analysis, partnerships are the least consistently specified of the action domains. Among the five countries that require (Ireland) or recommend (Czechia, France, the Netherlands, Portugal) partnerships, France refers to partnerships with non-governmental organisations and student organisations/initiatives, the Netherlands refers to partnerships with other higher education and/or research organisations, and Ireland notes external specialist agencies under “Other”, while two countries (Czechia, Portugal) do not specify the type of partnership. No country specifies partnerships with health services, community organisations, staff organisations/trade unions, other legal entities, or international partnerships in this item.

These results suggest that the “Partnership” dimension of the 7P framework is weakly operationalised in national instruments, often framed in general terms and rarely translated into explicit expectations about which external or sector actors/institutions should be engaged in addressing gender-based violence.

Figure 23. Specific Partnerships (N=5)

6.4 ACCOUNTABILITY

The Accountability pillar captures whether national frameworks include enforceable oversight mechanisms such as reporting duties, monitoring and evaluation requirements (including indicators), leadership accountability, and sanctions or consequences for non-compliance. The indicator synthesis identifies Accountability as the pillar with the widest spread across countries and underdeveloped in most countries. Four countries are classified as “comprehensive” (Austria, France, Ireland, and Sweden), six countries are classified as “emerging” (Czechia, Denmark, the Netherlands, Norway, Poland, and Portugal), and two as “absent” (Belgium, Lithuania). Thus, in many contexts, national frameworks do not institutionalise the system-level accountability architecture needed to ensure consistent implementation over time.

Figure 24. Comprehensiveness of the Accountability Pillar (N=12)

Countries with comprehensive accountability mechanisms: Countries that have at least five accountability elements in place, demonstrating strong monitoring, reporting, evaluation, leadership responsibility, and enforcement measures at national level.

4 Countries: Austria, France, Ireland, Sweden

Countries with developing accountability mechanisms: Countries that have at least four accountability elements in place, showing substantial but not yet full alignment with the expected monitoring, reporting, and enforcement requirements.

0 Countries

Countries with intermediary accountability mechanisms: Countries that have at least three accountability elements in place, reflecting a moderate level of oversight and institutional responsibility within the national framework.

0 Countries

Countries with emerging accountability mechanisms: Countries that have at least one accountability element in place, indicating early stage, limited, or partial structures for monitoring, reporting, or enforcing compliance.

6 Countries: Czechia, Denmark, the Netherlands, Poland, Portugal; Norway

Countries with absent accountability mechanisms: Countries that have none of the defined accountability elements in place, indicating no national provisions for oversight, reporting, evaluation, or enforcement.

2 Countries: *Belgium, Lithuania*

6.4.1 Regular Reporting Obligation

Countries that require the institutions covered to report regularly to national authorities on actions taken:

6 countries: *Austria, Czechia, France, Ireland, Portugal, Sweden*

Countries that do not require the institutions covered to report regularly to national authorities on actions taken:

6 countries: *Belgium, Denmark, Lithuania, the Netherlands, Poland, Norway*

Among the six countries that have a reporting requirement, reporting is most often framed as formal reporting and reporting on a regular basis:

- Formal reporting (4/6): Austria, Czechia, France, Ireland
- Informal reporting (1/6): Austria
- On a regular basis (3/6): Austria, Czechia, Ireland
- On an ad-hoc basis (1/6): Austria

Under “Other,” Portugal indicates that no specific reporting requirements are specified in the instrument. Sweden states that institutions are required to conduct formal annual reporting in relation to the gender mainstreaming assignment.

Figure 25. Reporting Obligation Elements (N=6)

6.4.2 Budget Reporting Obligation

Countries that require obliged institutions to report on the budgets allocated for addressing gender-based violence:

2 countries: *Austria, France*

Countries that do not require obliged institutions to report on the budgets allocated for addressing gender-based violence:

10 countries: *Belgium, Czechia, Denmark, Ireland, Lithuania, the Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Sweden, Norway*

Only Austria and France require that obliged institutions report on the budget. This budget reporting is part of other institutional reporting requirements.

Figure 26. Budget Reporting Elements (N=2)

6.4.3 Senior Management Responsibility

Countries that hold senior management (rectors, provosts) at the institutional level responsible for policy implementation:

6 countries: *Austria, France, Ireland, the Netherlands, Poland, Sweden*

Countries that do not hold senior management (rectors, provosts) at the institutional level responsible for policy implementation:

4 countries: *Belgium, Czechia, Lithuania, Portugal*

Six countries out of 12 report holding senior management responsible for implementation, in the following forms:

- Senior leadership role(s) responsible: Ireland, the Netherlands, Sweden
- Formal delegation / appointed officer(s) with defined duties: Austria and Poland

- Performance objectives for leadership and consequences for leadership in non-compliance: Austria

Without selecting a specific option, France indicates that the General Public Service Code enables strict enforcement of Gender Equality Plans, including gender-based violence measures, through financial penalties in cases of non-compliance.

Poland refers to provisions in the Law on Higher Education and Science under which the rector appoints disciplinary commissioners, may refer cases to mediation, impose an admonition for minor misconduct, or order the initiation of disciplinary proceedings.

Sweden adds that senior management, including the board of governors and the vice-chancellor, is formally responsible for implementing and upholding the ordinance's provisions, including those related to gender-based violence.

Denmark notes that the law does not explicitly specify senior management responsibility, but since institutions are required to have policies in place, this responsibility ultimately rests with the rector.

Norway reports that, according to interpretative reports on the University Act and the University College Act, the Board is held responsible for matters related to sexual harassment.

Figure 27. Specific Senior Management Responsibility (N=8)

6.4.4 Monitoring of Implementation

Countries that report that the national authority monitors the implementation of the instrument in place:

4 countries: *Austria, France, Ireland, Sweden*

Countries that report that the national authority does not monitor the implementation of the instrument in place:

3 countries: *Belgium, the Netherlands, Poland*

Countries that report that monitoring by the national authority is not applicable:

3 countries: *Lithuania, Portugal, Norway*

Countries that report that Other measures:

2 countries: *Czechia, Denmark*

Under “Other”, **Austria** states that monitoring takes place through the Supervisory Board four times per year and through Shareholder Meetings organised by the Ministry twice per year. **Denmark** reports that there is no monitoring at national level, while procedures at institutional level vary.

In Austria, Denmark, France, Ireland, and Sweden the monitoring is conducted by the policy owner. **Czechia** indicates that monitoring is conducted by the Centre for Gender and Science within the framework of the STRATIN project funded by the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports, with monitoring reports available for 2023 and 2024.

Figure 28. Monitoring Actor (N=6)

In terms of **frequency**, annual monitoring is conducted in Czechia, France, Ireland, and Sweden. **Austria** states that monitoring takes place through the Supervisory Board four times per year and through Shareholder Meetings organised by the Ministry twice per year. **Denmark** indicates that monitoring is framed as institutional rather than national.

Figure 29. Monitoring Frequency (N=6)

In the six countries that indicate that monitoring takes place (Austria, Czechia, Denmark, France, Ireland, and Sweden), it is **both qualitative and quantitative**.

None of the countries give a clear “Yes” to a question about a **budget provided to conduct the monitoring**. France, Czechia, Sweden report “No”, while Austria, Denmark, and Ireland use “Other” to indicate monitoring is embedded in existing roles/planning or institutional-level arrangements rather than a dedicated monitoring budget. Austria states that monitoring and annual implementation planning are embedded in the governance of performance agreements, with the budget indirectly included within these agreements. Denmark indicates that a budget is available at institutional level, where monitoring forms part of the work of Human Resources. Ireland reports that monitoring is covered as part of the role of a dedicated staff member within the Higher Education Authority.

Figure 30. Monitoring Budget (N=6)

Four countries (Austria, Denmark, Ireland, Sweden) report that the monitoring is used for further policy development.

Figure 31. Monitoring for Policy Development (N=6)

6.4.5 Monitoring Indicators

Countries that report the existence of monitoring indicators:

2 countries: *France, the Netherlands*

Countries that do not report the existence of monitoring indicators:

8 countries: *Belgium, Czechia, Denmark, Lithuania, Poland, Portugal, Sweden, Norway*

Formal indicators are present in very few cases, and several countries rely on broader governance arrangements rather than indicator-based accountability.

Austria indicates that the main instrument includes key performance indicators (KPIs). **Ireland** reports that while the main instrument does not itself define monitoring indicators for higher education institutions, the reporting template requires each institution to provide an indicator for each outcome, either using a suggested indicator or defining its own. At national level, aggregated, self-assessed ratings of institutional progress against the Framework outcomes are used as indicators, such as the percentage of institutions reporting good progress on a specific outcome.

6.4.6 Sanctions or Consequences for Non-compliance

These countries report that sanctions or consequences are foreseen in the event that obliged institutions do not comply with the instrument:

5 countries: *Austria, France, Ireland, Poland, Sweden*

These countries report that sanctions or consequences are not foreseen in the event that obliged institutions do not comply with the instrument:

4 countries: *Belgium, Czechia, the Netherlands, Portugal*

These countries report that the question of sanctions or consequences is not applicable:

1 country: *Denmark*

Of the five countries that report sanctions or consequences in case of non-compliance, **Ireland** and **Sweden** have in place corrective action plans and timelines for remediation/response. Funding conditionality / financial consequences is implemented in **France**. Administrative penalties and referral to oversight/equality/ombuds bodies are foreseen in **Austria** and **Sweden**.

Austria further specifies that follow-up mechanisms exist but are complaint-driven and handled on a case-by-case basis by the Equal Treatment Commission rather than through systematic proactive monitoring.

Poland refers to the Law on Higher Education and Science, which provides that disciplinary proceedings concerning academic teachers are governed by the Code of Criminal Procedure where not otherwise specified, and mandates the minister responsible for higher education and science to regulate in detail the procedures for mediation, investigation, and disciplinary proceedings, including the serving and expungement of disciplinary penalties.

Lithuania indicates that sanctions fall within the competence of the Labour Inspectorate.

Norway reports that the Anti-Discrimination Tribunal may issue decisions or statements confirming that a violation of the relevant legislation, including the Equality and Anti-Discrimination Act, has occurred.

None of the responding countries report any specific follow-up measures for non-compliant institutions, with answers indicating that no follow-up is mentioned, foreseen, or specified in the instrument.

Figure 32. Specific Sanctions or Consequences for Non-Compliance (N=7)

6.4.7 Evaluation of Policy Effectiveness

These countries report that the national authority **evaluates the effectiveness of the main instrument:**

5 countries: Denmark, Ireland, the Netherlands, Sweden, Norway

These countries report that the national authority **does not evaluate the effectiveness of the main instrument:**

6 countries: Austria, Belgium, Czechia, France, Poland, Portugal

Figure 33. Frequency of Evaluation (N=6)

In terms of frequency, **Denmark** and **Norway** report **ad hoc** evaluation, with **Denmark** specifying that reviews take place when legislative amendments are introduced and **Norway** noting limited clarity regarding the concrete follow up arrangements. **Ireland** and **Sweden** report **periodic evaluation**, with **Ireland** indicating that a policy review is conducted after five years of implementation and **Sweden** describing regular evaluation under the Higher Education Ordinance with prioritisation and follow up to ensure continuous quality assurance. **The Netherlands** reports annual evaluation, without further specification on the procedure.

In terms of **who conducts the evaluation**, **Denmark** and **Norway** indicate the policy owner as the evaluator; **Ireland** indicates an independent expert group convened for this purpose, with support from the national authority; **the Netherlands** reports that monitoring of experienced social safety is carried out by higher education institutions themselves; **Sweden** specifies that evaluation and monitoring of the Higher Education Ordinance is conducted by the Swedish Higher Education Authority, an independent government agency under the Ministry of Education and Research; and **Lithuania** indicates that the Labour Inspectorate is responsible for evaluation.

Figure 34. Evaluation Actor (N=6)

The **availability of a budget for evaluation** is reported by **Ireland** and **the Netherlands**.

Under “Other,” **Denmark** states that amendments of laws are considered part of the regular work of politicians, implying no separate budget line for evaluation.

In terms of the **form of evaluation**, only **Ireland** and **Sweden** explicitly tick both qualitative and quantitative forms; other countries that indicated that evaluation is conducted did not specify the form. **The Netherlands** reports that the monitoring instrument is still under development.

Denmark, Ireland, and Sweden foresee the use of evaluation for **further policy development**.

Figure 35. Evaluation Form (N=6)

6.4.8 Public Messaging on Policy Adoption

These countries report that there **has been specific public messaging around the policy adoption and launch:**

5 countries: *Austria, France, Ireland, Lithuania, Sweden*

These countries report that there **has not been specific public messaging around the policy adoption and launch:**

5 countries: *Belgium, Czechia, Denmark, the Netherlands, Poland*

Portugal and Norway report that they are not sure whether there has been any specific public messaging around the policy adoption and launch.

Figure 36. Form of Public Messaging (N=7)

Of the five countries that reported public messaging, this tended to be limited to the **public launch of the policy** (Austria, France, Ireland, and Lithuania) with the **highest-ranking official present** for the event in France and Ireland.

6.4.9 Provisions on Multi-Site Serial Misconduct

These countries report that the instrument **includes provisions to counteract multi-site serial misconduct by the same perpetrators at different institutions:**

1 country: *Austria*

These countries report that the instrument **does not include provisions to counteract multi-site serial misconduct by the same perpetrators at different institutions:**

11 countries: *Belgium, Czechia, Denmark, France, Ireland, Lithuania, the Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Sweden; Norway*

Austria is the only country to address multi-site serial misconduct, and this includes safeguards related to data protection, due process, and confidentiality. This policy element therefore represents an almost universal gap despite the relevance of mobility and cross-institutional careers in higher education and research and innovation.

7. CONCLUSIONS

This monitoring demonstrates a policy landscape which is maturing rapidly in several national contexts, with visible advances since 2023. Progress nevertheless remains uneven across the European Research Area: required or recommended actions are more frequently specified than system-level accountability provisions, while persistent gaps concern the conceptual framing of policies, including recognition of gender-based violence as a systemic issue, coverage of priority groups, and explicit zero tolerance principles.

These conclusions are also informed by a policy debate held at the report launch on 19 March 2026 with representatives of Austria, Spain, Ireland and Poland. The discussion reinforced that policy advances are most likely where political leadership aligns with a strong evidence base and structured stakeholder engagement, and that implementation depends on sustained resources, practical support and embedded accountability mechanisms that can withstand shifts in political context.

7.1 POLICY IMPLICATIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Strengthen conceptual alignment (Commitment)

- **Advance the Commitment dimension.** Strengthen recognition of gender-based violence as a systemic issue, expand coverage of priority groups, and embed explicit zero-tolerance principles within national policy frameworks.
- **Translate zero tolerance into operational standards.** Make victim-/survivor-centred and trauma-informed approaches, a whole-institution approach, and clear standards for responding to all forms of gender-based violence explicit in national instruments, so that institutional action is guided by a shared conceptual baseline.

Embed Accountability as system governance

- **Strengthen accountability architectures and learn from existing national-level approaches.** National authorities and the European Commission should prioritise system-level accountability provisions including monitoring and review cycles with indicators, clear leadership accountability, and proportionate corrective mechanisms for non-compliance.
- **Prevent backsliding by embedding requirements in established system levers.** Use governance instruments such as performance agreements, reporting templates, funding conditions, and quality assurance processes to institutionalise responsibilities and accountability, rather than relying only on standalone strategies.

Strengthen policy focus on higher education and research and minimum standards

- **Develop instruments specific for higher education and research and innovation.** Where only general frameworks exist, develop dedicated instruments or structured support programmes tailored to higher education and research and innovation that clarify responsibilities across staff and students and across organisational types (including private actors where relevant).

- **Clarify institutional responsibilities and minimum standards.** Where national instruments require action, specify minimum expectations more clearly (e.g., reporting channels, protection against retaliation, investigation safeguards, and access to services), supported by practical implementation guidance and templates.

Resource implementation and improve transparency

- **Make resourcing visible and sustainable.** Increase transparency of financing and ensure resources reach institutions to operationalise a comprehensive set of actions across the 7P framework. Budget transparency should be treated as a core accountability requirement.
- **Increase visibility and transparency of policy instruments.** Limited public messaging and limited accessible documentation hinder awareness, uptake, and monitoring. National authorities should ensure that instruments, expectations, and support are publicly available and communicated beyond policy circles.

Address mobility and cross-institutional risks

- **Strengthen cross-institutional cooperation to address mobility-related risks.** Few frameworks address cases spanning more than one institution or multi-site serial misconduct. EU and national coordination should prioritise legally sound mechanisms for cross-institutional cooperation to prevent “passing the perpetrator.”

Use EU coordination and stakeholder engagement to support further progress

- **Build broad stakeholder coalitions without shifting responsibility onto students.** Structured engagement with institutional leadership, staff organisations, students, experts, and specialised organisations supports legitimacy and implementation quality, while responsibility for change must remain with institutions and systems.
- **Use EU coordination and mutual learning to support further progress.** Continue to use ERA governance and Communities of Practice to share models beyond the current core of active countries.
- **Use upcoming EU milestones as leverage for alignment.** The transposition period for the Directive on combating violence against women and domestic violence provides an entry point to mainstream minimum standards for higher education and research and innovation and strengthens accountability expectations into national frameworks. Additional important policy developments include the ERA Act and negotiations of Horizon Europe 2028 – 2034 where the Gender Equality Plan eligibility criterion is of relevance, including the thematic area of gender-based violence.

7.2 IMPLICATIONS FOR FUTURE MONITORING

- **Address complexity and variability across countries through clearer definitions.** Strengthen the glossary and add “how-to-classify” guidance (dedicated instrument vs. general instrument vs. initiative) to reduce interpretive variance.
- **Refine the questionnaire to capture policy mixes more consistently.** Improve how the tool distinguishes between general and dedicated instruments and how it captures where accountability provisions sit.
- **Improve capture of where accountability “sits” in the system.** Add a light-touch item documenting whether accountability requirements are anchored in system instruments (e.g., performance agreements, funding conditionality, inspectorate/quality assurance processes) and whether these link to reporting and review cycles.
- **Increase participation and reduce respondent burden.** Use a modular approach (short core module + optional deep dives where a dedicated instrument exists) and maintain helpdesk support and reminders to improve coverage and completeness.
- **Strengthen transparency requirements to improve verifiability.** Require standard references for each instrument (title, year, official link) and encourage public availability of key documents. Limited public information made assessment difficult in several cases.
- **Improve capture of devolved/federal variation.** Develop a structured approach for regional data collection in devolved systems so that sub-national dynamics are not lost (and to avoid mixing regional detail into national-level comparability).

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APPENDIX

APPENDIX 1. OPERATIONALISATION OF THE INDICATORS

Appendix 1 documents the classification logic underpinning the five indicator maps presented in this report. It sets out how questionnaire responses were operationalised into categorical indicators, assigning each country to one of five development levels (**Comprehensive, Developing, Intermediary, Emerging, or Absent**) based on predefined conditions (for design details, see Section 5.2 of the GenderSAFE Deliverable 5.2). For each indicator, the tables specify (i) the conceptual criteria defining each level and (ii) the corresponding questionnaire items and response codes used for assignment, ensuring transparency and replicability of the coding.

Table 1. Overall comprehensiveness of the national legal and policy framework

Comprehensive	A dedicated policy OR law OR both is in place	B1 = 1
Developing	A more general policy OR law OR both, AND a dedicated initiative are in place	B2a = (7-12) AND B3=1
Intermediary	A more general policy OR law is in place OR dedicated initiatives are in place	B2a = (7-12) OR B3=1
Emerging	A National Action Plan or equivalent policy, to counteract all forms of gender-based violence and/or violence against women without a specific mention of higher education and/or research is in place	B2A = (3-6)
Absent	A general law to address gender equality and/or violence against women is in place	B2A = 1 or 2

Table 2. Policy Outlook

Strengthened policy	There are documented plans by the national/regional authority to strengthen the policies to counteract gender-based violence in higher education and/or research and innovation in EITHER:	IF B16 includes any (1–10)
	- upcoming national/regional laws dedicated to addressing gender-based violence in higher education and/or research and innovation OR	
	- upcoming national/regional generic laws OR	
	- upcoming national/regional policies dedicated to addressing gender-based violence in higher education and/or research and innovation	
	- upcoming national/regional generic policies OR	

	- upcoming national/regional initiatives.	
Unchanged policy	There are no documented plans to either strengthen or weaken policies addressing gender-based violence in higher education or research and innovation by the national/regional authority.	B16 = 11 AND B17 = 7
Weakened policy	There are documented plans by the national/regional authority to weaken policies to counteract gender-based violence in higher education/research and innovation in:	IF B17 includes any (1- 6)
	- upcoming national/regional laws OR	
	- upcoming national/regional policies OR	
	- upcoming national/regional initiatives	

Table 3. Commitment

Comprehensive	4 elements of the systemic nature of gender-based violence are recognised AND at least 7 priority groups and protected characteristics are defined AND at least 4 of the zero-tolerance principles are addressed in the main policy/action selected above	C2=1 AND C2a all selected (1-4) AND C3=1 AND C3a at least 7 selected (1-16) AND C4=1 AND C4a at least 4 selected (1-6)
Developing	3 elements of the systemic nature of gender-based violence are recognised AND at least 5 priority groups are defined AND at least 3 the zero-tolerance principles are addressed in the main policy/action selected above	C2=1 AND C2a at least 3 selected (1-4) AND C3=1 AND C3a at least 5 selected (1-16) AND C4=1 AND C4a at least 3 selected (1-6)
Intermediary	2 elements of the systemic nature of gender-based violence are recognised AND/OR at least 3 priority groups are defined AND/OR at least 2 the zero-tolerance principles are addressed in the main policy/action selected above	C2=1 AND C2a at least 2 selected (1-4) AND/OR C3=1 AND C3a at least 3 selected (1-16) AND/OR C4=1 AND C4a at least 2 selected (1-6)
Emerging	1 or 2 elements of the systemic nature of gender-based violence are recognised OR at least 3 priority groups are defined OR at least 1 of the zero-tolerance principles are addressed in the main policy/action selected above	C2=1 AND C2a at least 1 selected (1-4) AND/OR C3=1 AND C3a at least 3 selected (1-16) AND/OR C4=1 AND C4a at least 1 selected (1-6)
Absent	The main policy/action selected above does not recognise the systemic nature of gender-based violence, does not define priority groups and does not define any of the zero-tolerance principles	C2=2 AND C3=2 AND C4=2

Table 4. Action

Comprehensive	The national/regional authority requires and/or recommends that at least 8 of the actions below be put in place by the institutions covered by the policy:	At least 8 are true
	- institutional policy in place	D3a = 1
	- institutional monitoring and evaluation	D3a = 2 OR 4

	- prevalence/incidence and data collection measures	D4 = 1 OR 2
	- preventative measures	D5 = 1 OR 2
	- capacity building for leadership	D6 = 1 OR 2
	- protective measures	D7 = 1 OR 2
	- investigative/disciplinary actions	D8 = 1 OR 2
	- provision of services	D9 = 1 OR 2
	- partnerships	D10 = 1 OR 2
Developing	The national/regional authority requires and/or recommends that at least 6 of the actions below be put in place by the institutions covered by the policy:	At least 6 are true
	- institutional policy in place	D3a = 1
	- institutional monitoring and evaluation	D3a = 2 OR 4
	- prevalence/incidence and data collection measures	D4 = 1 OR 2
	- preventative measures	D5 = 1 OR 2
	- capacity building for senior leadership	D6 = 1 OR 2
	- protective measures	D7 = 1 OR 2
	investigative/disciplinary actions	D8 = 1 OR 2
	- provision of services	D9 = 1 OR 2
- partnerships	D10 = 1 OR 2	
Intermediary	The national/regional authority requires and/or recommends that at least 4 of the actions below be put in place by the institutions covered by the policy:	At least 4 are true
	- institutional policy in place	D3a = 1
	- institutional monitoring and evaluation	D3a = 2 OR 4
	- prevalence/incidence and data collection measures	D4 = 1 OR 2
	- preventative measures	D5 = 1 OR 2
	- capacity building for senior leadership	D6 = 1 OR 2
	- protective measures	D7 = 1 OR 2
	investigative/disciplinary actions	D8 = 1 OR 2
	- provision of services	D9 = 1 OR 2
- partnerships	D10 = 1 OR 2	
Emerging	The national/regional authority requires and/or recommends that at least 2 of the actions below be put in place by the institutions covered by the policy:	At least 2 are true
	- institutional policy in place	D3a = 1
	- institutional monitoring and evaluation	D3a = 2 OR 4
	- prevalence/incidence and data collection measures	D4 = 1 OR 2
	- preventative measures	D5 = 1 OR 2
	- capacity building for senior leadership	D6 = 1 OR 2
	- protective measures	D7 = 1 OR 2
	investigative/disciplinary actions	D8 = 1 OR 2
	- provision of services	D9 = 1 OR 2
- partnerships	D10 = 1 OR 2	
Absent	The national/regional authority requires and/or recommends none of the actions below be put in place by the institutions covered by the policy:	D2=2
	- institutional policy in place	
	- institutional monitoring and evaluation	
	- prevalence/incidence and data collection measures	
	- preventative measures	

	- capacity building for senior leadership	
	- protective measures	
	investigative/disciplinary actions	
	- provision of services	
	- partnerships	

Table 5. Accountability

Comprehensive	At least five of the following accountability elements are in place:	At least 5 are true
	- The national/regional authority conducts policy monitoring at the national/regional level, including through indicators	E5 = 1
	- The national/regional authority conducts policy evaluation at the national/regional level	E8 = 1
	- The national/regional authority requires reports from the institutions on institutional policies, actions and measures taken	E2 = 1
	- The national/regional authority requires reports on the institutional budgets allocated for policy/action implementation	E3 = 1
	- The national/regional authority holds senior management of the institutions accountable for institutional policy implementation	E4 = 1
	- The national/regional authority has sanctions in place for non-compliance by the institutions covered by the policy.	E7 = 1
Developing	At least four of the following accountability elements are in place:	At least 4 are true
	- The national/regional authority conducts policy monitoring at the national/regional level, including through indicators	E5 = 1
	- The national/regional authority conducts policy evaluation at the national/regional level	E8 = 1
	- The national/regional authority requires reports from the institutions on institutional policies, actions and measures taken	E2 = 1
	- The national/regional authority requires reports on the institutional budgets allocated for policy/action implementation	E3 = 1
	- The national/regional authority holds senior management of the institutions accountable for institutional policy implementation	E4 = 1
	- The national/regional authority has sanctions in place for non-compliance by the institutions covered by the policy.	E7 = 1
Intermediary	At least three of the following accountability elements are in place:	At least 3 are true
	- The national/regional authority conducts policy monitoring at the national/regional level, including through indicators	E5 = 1
	- The national/regional authority conducts policy evaluation at the national/regional level	E8 = 1
	- The national/regional authority requires reports from the institutions on institutional policies, actions and measures taken	E2 = 1
	- The national/regional authority requires reports on the institutional budgets allocated for policy/action implementation	E3 = 1
	- The national/regional authority holds senior management of the institutions accountable for institutional policy implementation	E4 = 1
	- The national/regional authority has sanctions in place for non-compliance by the institutions covered by the policy.	E7 = 1

Emerging	At least one of the following accountability elements are in place:	At least 1 is true
	- The national/regional authority conducts policy monitoring at the national/regional level, including through indicators	E5 = 1
	- The national/regional authority conducts policy evaluation at the national/regional level	E8 = 1
	- The national/regional authority requires reports from the institutions on institutional policies, actions and measures taken	E2 = 1
	- The national/regional authority requires reports on the institutional budgets allocated for policy/action implementation	E3 = 1
	- The national/regional authority holds senior management of the institutions accountable for institutional policy implementation	E4 = 1
	- The national/regional authority has sanctions in place for non-compliance by the institutions covered by the policy.	E7 = 1
Absent	None of the above	E2 = 2

APPENDIX 2. OVERVIEW OF NATIONAL INSTRUMENTS

Country	Complexity of instruments	Title of Instrument	Responsible Authority	Adoption/Amendment Year	Timeframe	Policy-mix
Austria	Developing	Austrian Action Plan for the European Research Area (ERA-NAP) 2022-2025	Ministry of Women, Science and Research; Ministry of Innovation, Mobility and Infrastructure; Ministry of Economy, Energy and Tourism	Adoption 2022	2022-2025	Yes
		Federal Equal Opportunities Act	Federal Chancellery (Federal Equal Treatment Commissions are supervised by the Federal Ministry of Women, Science and Research)	Adoption: 1993; Amendments: last 2025	1993- open-ended	
		Equal Opportunities Act	Federal Ministry of Labour, Social Affairs, Health, Care and Consumer Protection; Federal Ministry of Woman, Science and Research	Adoption: 2005; Amendments: last 2023	2005- open-ended	
		Violence Protection Strategy for Coordination and Networking with a Focus on Counselling for Women Affected by Violence in Austria	Federal Ministry of Women, Science and Research	Adoption: 2024	2024- open-ended	
		Universities Act 2002 - UG	Federal Ministry of Women, Science and Research	Adoption: 2002; Amendments: last 2025	2002- open-ended	
		Violence Protection Act	Federal Ministry of Justice	Adoption: 1997; Amendments: 2009, 2019	1997- open-ended	
		National Action Plan Against Violence Towards Women	Federal Government	Adoption: 2025	2025-2029	
		Performance and Financing Agreements with Public RFOs (Gender Equality and GBV-related Measures)	Ministry for Innovation, Mobility and Infrastructure	Start: 2021; Renewal: every 3 years	2021- open-ended	
		Performance Agreements between the BMFWF and public universities	Ministry of Women, Science and Research	Start: 2007; Renewal: every 3 years	Open-ended	
		Studies on various topics and areas of gender-based violence assigned by different Federal Ministries	Depends on the study.	ongoing	open-ended	
Belgium	Comprehensive	Decree on Transgressive Behaviour in Higher Education	Flemish authority: the Minister-President and the Minister for Education	Adoption: 2023	2023- open-ended	Yes
		Charter Transgressive Behaviour	Flemish Minister for Education	Adoption: 2018	2018- open-ended	

		Circular 9037 of 18/09/2023 Prevention and combating of harassment, discrimination and sexual violence in higher education and social advancement education establishments in the Wallonia-Brussels Federation	Minister for education for the French speaking Community	Adoption: 2023	2023- open-ended	
		National Action Plan on Gender-Based Violence 2021-2025	Federal authority, Regions, Communities, under coordination by the Institute for the Equality of Women and Men	Adoption: 2019; Amendments:	2021-2025	
		Brussels / Flemish Walloon Region/French speaking Community/COCOF Regional Action Plans on Gender-Based Violence	Regional governments	Adoption: 2021	2022-2024	
		Working Group Transgressive Behaviour	Flemish Interuniversity Council (VLIR)	Start: 2022	2022- open-ended	
Bulgaria	Absent	Law on Equality between Women and Men	Council of Ministers of the Republic of Bulgaria, Ministry of Labour and Social Policy	Adoption: 2016; Amendments: last 2023	2016- open-ended	NA
		Law on Protection Against Discrimination	National Assembly of the Republic of Bulgaria, Commission for Protection against Discrimination	Adoption: 2004; Amendments: last 2023	2004- open-ended	
Croatia	Emerging	Act on Gender Equality	Gender Equality Office of the Government of the Republic of Croatia	Adoption: 2008; Amendments: 2017	2008-	Yes
		National Plan for Gender Equality for the period until 2027	Gender Equality Office of the Government of the Republic of Croatia	Adoption: 2023	2023-2027	
		National Plan for the Suppression of Sexual Violence and Sexual Harassment for the period until 2027	Ministry of Labour, Pension System, Family and Social Policy	Adoption: 2022	2022-2027	
		National Plan for the Protection and Promotion of Human Rights and Combatting Discrimination until 2027	Office for Human Rights and Rights of National Minorities of the Government of the Republic of Croatia	Adoption: 2023	2023-2027	
		Action Plan for the Promotion and Establishment of Gender Equality of the Ministry of Science and Education 2023–2026	Ministry of Science, Education and Youth	Adoption: 2023	2023-2026	

Czechia	Developing	Act No. 111/1998 Coll., on Higher Education Institutions and on Amendments and Supplements to other acts (Higher Education Act), as Amended, and other Related Acts	Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports	Adoption: 1998; Amendments: 2025	1998- open-ended	Yes
		Gender Equality Strategy 2021 - 2030	Office of the Government of the Czech Republic	Adoption: 2021; Amendments: 2024	2021-2030	
		Strategic Plan of the Ministry for Higher Education for the Period from 2021	Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports	Adoption: 2020	2021-2030	
		Action Plan for the Prevention of Domestic and Gender-Based Violence for 2023–2026 of 23 August 2023	Office of the Government of the Czech Republic	Adoption: 2023	2023-2026	
		Resolution No. 29/2025 of the Governmental Council for Gender Equality on Supporting Women in Science and Research	Governmental Council for Gender Equality	Adoption: 2025	2025 – open-ended	
		Resolution No. 7/2023 of the Governmental Council for Gender Equality on Gender-Based Violence at Universities	Governmental Council for Gender Equality	Adoption: 2023	2023- open-ended	
		Minimum Standard for a Safe Environment for High-Quality, Sustainable, and Free Research and Educational Activities	-	Adoption: 2024	2024- open-ended	
		Template for Annual Reports of Higher Education Institutions 2024	Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports	Start: 2017; Amendment: 2024	2017	
Denmark	Developing	Principles for Anti-harassment Policy in the Educational Environment Act	Ministry of Higher Education and Science + Ministry of Children and Education	Adoption: 2024	2024- open-ended	Yes
		Working Environment Act and Executive Order on the Psychological Work Environment	Danish Ministry of Employment	Adoption: 1985; Amendments: last 2025	1985- open-ended	
		The Danish University Act	Danish Ministry of Higher Education and Science	Adoption: 2003; Amendments: last 2025	2003- open-ended	
		Law on the Protection of Whistleblowers	Ministry of Justice	Adoption: 2021; Amendments: 2024	2021- open-ended	

		The Danish Equal Treatment Act	Ministry of Employment	Adoption: 1989; Amendments: last 2024	1989- open-ended	
		Gender Equality Act	Ministry of Gender Equality	Adoption: 2000; Amendments: last 2025	2000- open-ended	
		The National 'Perspectives and Action Plan'	Ministry of Gender Equality	Adoption: 2025	2025	
		Justice Act	Ministry of Justice	Adoption: 1986; Amendments: last 2020	1986- open-ended	
		The Danish National Action Plan for Women, Peace and Security 2025 2029	Ministry of Gender Equality, Ministry of Defence, Ministry of Justice, Ministry of Foreign Affairs of Denmark, Ministry of Immigration and Integration, Ministry of Resilience and Preparedness	Adoption: 2025	2025-2029	
		The Danish Working Environment Authority's Executive Order no. 1406 of 26 September 2020 on psychosocial working environment by the Ministry of Employment	Ministry of Employment	Adoption: 2020	2020- open-ended	
		Webinars: Let's Talk, Let's Act	Ministry of Higher Education and Science	One-off		
		Recommendations for Addressing Discrimination in Danish Higher Education Based on the GENDERACTIONplus Webinar Series "Let's Talk, Let's Act: Addressing Discrimination in Danish Higher Education"	Ministry of Higher Education and Science	Start: 2025	One-off	
Finland	Absent	Non-Discrimination Act	Ministry of Justice	Adoption: 2014; Amendments: last 2024	2014 – open-ended	Yes
		Act on Equality Between Women and Men	Ministry of Social Affairs and Health	Adoption: 1986; Amendments: last 2023	1986 – open-ended	
		Occupational Safety And Health Act	Ministry of Social Affairs and Health	Adoption: 2002; Amendments: last 2025	2002 – open-ended	
		Funding requirements of main funders, see here and here	Business Finland and Research Council of Finland			

France	Comprehensive	National action plan against sexist and sexual violence in higher education and research	The Ministry of Higher Education, Research and Space	Adoption: 2021	2021-2025	Yes
		General Public Service Code	General Directorate for Administration and Civil Service	Adoption: 2019	2019 – open-ended	
		Code of Education: the Law No. 2025-732 of 31 July 2025 on combating antisemitism in higher education modifies the Code of Education	Ministry of Education and Ministry of Higher Education, Research and Space	Adoption: 2000; Amendments: last 2025	2000 – open-ended	
Ireland	Comprehensive	Safe, Respectful, Supportive and Positive: Ending Sexual Violence and Harassment in Irish Higher Education Institutions	Higher Education Authority	Adoption: 2019	2019- open-ended (planned review after 5 years)	Yes
		HEA Ending Sexual Violence and Harassment Implementation Plan	Higher Education Authority	Adoption: 2022	2022-2025	
		Zero Tolerance: The Third National Strategy on Domestic, Sexual and Gender-Based Violence Implementation Plan 2025–2026	CUAN	Adoption: 2025	2025-2026	
		Speak Out Anonymous Reporting Tool	Speak Out National Office (funded by the Higher Education Authority)	Adoption: 2021; Amendments: 2024	2021- open-ended (review in 2026)	
Lithuania	Intermediary	Law on Equal Opportunities for Women and Men	Office of the Equal Opportunities Ombudsman and Ministry of Social Security and Labour	Adoption: 1998; Amendments: 2024	1998- open-ended	
		Labour Code of the Republic of Lithuania (2016)	State Labour Inspectorate	Adoption: 2016; Amendments: 2024	2016- open-ended	
		Law on Higher Education and Research	Ministry of Education, Science and Sport	Adoption: 2009; Amendments: 2025	2009-unspecified	
		Guidelines on the Prevention of Sexual Harassment and Handling of Cases	Rector's Conference	Adoption: 2020	2020- open-ended	
Netherlands	Comprehensive	Integral Policy on Social Safety in Higher Education and Science	Ministry of Education, Culture and Science	Adoption: 2023	2023-2031	Yes
		Programme Social Safety in Higher Education and Science	Ministry of Education, Culture and Science	Adoption: 2024	2024-2027	

		Subsidy Scheme on Social Safety in Higher Education and Science (as part of the Programme previously mentioned)	Ministry of Education, Culture and Science	Adoption: 2025	2025-2027	
		Action Programme Sexually Transgressive Behaviour and Sexual Violence	The Ministry of Education, Culture and Science and the Ministry of Social Affairs and Employment on behalf of the entire government	Adoption: 2023	2023-2026	
		Conference on Social Safety in Higher Education and Science	Ministry of Education, Culture and Science	Adoption: 2025	2025-2027	
Poland	Developing	Convention on Preventing and Combating Violence Against Women and Domestic Violence (Istanbul Convention)	Ministry of Family, Labour and Social Policy	Adoption: 2015	2015- open-ended	Yes
		The Labour Code	Ministry of Family, Labour and Social Policy	Adoption: 1974; Amendments: last 2025	1974-unspecified	
		Law on Higher Education and Science	Ministry of Science and Higher Education	Adoption: 2018; Amendments: last 2025	2018- open-ended	
		Academia Without Violence (a series of trainings and workshops delivered by legal and mental-health specialists)	Co-financed by the Ministry of Science and Higher Education and implemented by an NGO (Discover Your Mind Foundation)	Adoption: 2025	2025	
		What is allowed at a university? Undesired behaviours and how to respond when they occur (a series of trainings for students, doctoral candidates, and university staff)	Co-financed by the Ministry of Science and Higher Education and implemented by the Academic Network for Safety and Equality	Adoption: 2025	2025	
		Gender Equality Plans in Scientific Institutions in Poland. An Analysis of Implementation Status	Ministry for Science and Higher Education	Adoption: 2024	2024	
		Comfort Zone Project	Ministry of Science and Higher Education, commissioned the task reg. this initiative to Students' Parliament of the Republic of Poland.	Adoption: 2025	2025-2026	
		The Ministerial Academic Debate Forum (a series of meetings with researchers and practitioners)	Ministry of Science and Higher Education	Adoption: 2024; Amendments:	2024- open-ended	

		involved in mental health in academia)				
Portugal	Comprehensive	Law n. 61/2023 (Creates psychological support responses for victims of sexual harassment and violence in higher education.)	Assembly of the Republic (the Portuguese Parliament)	Adoption: 2023	2023- open-ended	No
		Order n. 6560/2023 (Creation of a commission to develop a strategy for the prevention of harassment in higher education institutions.)	Joint Order of the Offices of the Minister in the Cabinet of the Prime Minister and for Parliamentary Affair, the Minister of Science, Technology and Higher Education, and the Minister of Labour, Solidarity and Social Security	Adoption: 2023	2023- open-ended	
		Order n. 5604-A/2024 (Creates a commission to monitor the implementation of strategies to prevent harassment in higher education institutions.)	Joint Order of the Offices of the Minister of Education, Science and Innovation, the Minister of Labour, Solidarity and Social Security, and the Minister of Youth and Modernisation	Adoption: 2024	2024- open-ended	
		Resolution of the Assembly of the Republic N. 4/2013 (Approval of Istanbul Convention)	Assembly of the Republic (the Portuguese Parliament)	Adoption: 2013	2013- open-ended	
		Law n. 112/2009 (Establishes the legal framework applicable to the prevention of domestic violence, the protection and assistance of its victims)	Assembly of the Republic (the Portuguese Parliament)	Adoption: 2009; Amendments: last 2021	2009- open-ended	
		Resolution of the Council of Ministers N. 61/2018 (Approves the National Strategy for Equality and Non-Discrimination)	Council of Ministers	Adoption: 2018; Amendments: last 2023	2018-2030	
		Monitoring and Guidance Framework by the National Commission for the Prevention of Harassment in Higher Education	National Commission for the Prevention of Harassment in Higher Education	Adoption: 2024	2024	

		CIG — National Services, Complaint Portals and Training for Strategic Audiences	Commission for Citizenship and Gender Equality (CIG)	Adoption: 1997	1997- open-ended	
Slovakia	Emerging	National Action Plan for the Prevention and Elimination of Violence Against Women for the Years 2022–2027	Ministry of Labour, Social Affairs and Family of the Slovak Republic	Adoption: 2022	2022-2027	Yes
		Action Plan for Gender Equality and Equal Opportunities 2021–2027	Ministry of Labour, Social Affairs and Family of the Slovak Republic	Adopted: 2021	2021–2027	
		National Strategy for Equality Between Women and Men and Equal Opportunities in the Slovak Republic for the years 2021-2027	Ministry of Labour, Social Affairs and Family of the Slovak Republic	Adoption: 2021	2021-2027	
		Fair Academia	Slovak Centre of Scientific and Technical Information and Žijem Vedu (Living Science)	Start: 2022	Organized annually	
Sweden	Intermediary	The Higher Education Ordinance (1993:100)	Swedish Council for Higher Education	Adoption: 1993; Amendments: last 2025	1993-uspecified	Yes
		The Discrimination Act (2008:567)	Ombudsman with local ombudsman at universities	Adoption: 2001; Amendments: 2007	2001- open-ended	
		Gender Mainstreaming Requirement in Universities	All universities	Adoption: varies	varies	
		Gender Equality Policy in Sweden	The Swedish Government	Adoption: 1994; Amendments: last 2024	1994- open-ended	
Albania	Emerging	National Strategy for Gender Equality 2021–2030	Ministry of Health and Social Protection of Albania	Adoption: 2021	2021-2030	Yes
		Law No. 9970/2008 “Gender Equality in Society”	Ministry of Health and Social Protection of Albania	Adoption: 2008	2008- open-ended	
		Law No. 9669/2006 “On Measures Against Violence in Family Relations”	Ministry of Health and Social Protection of Albania	Adoption: 2006	2006- open-ended	
Iceland	Emerging	Policy, Prevention and Response Plan of the Government Regarding Bullying, Gender Based Harassment, Sexual Harassment and Violence	Ministry of Social Affairs and Housing	Adoption: 2015; Amendments: 2023	2015- open-ended	Yes
		Regulation on Measures Against Bullying, Sexual Harassment,	Ministry of Culture, Innovation and Higher Education	Adoption: 2015; Amendments:2023	2015- open-ended	

		Gender-Based Harassment and Violence in the Workplace				
		Act on Working Environment, Health and Safety in Workplaces	Ministry of Social Affairs and Housing	Adoption: 1980; Amendments: last 2024	1980- open-ended	
Norway	Intermediary	The Universities and University Colleges Act	Ministry of Education and Research	Adoption: 2005; Amendments: 2024	2005- open-ended	Yes
		Strategy for Gender Equality 2025–2030	The Norwegian Ministry of Culture and Equality	Adoption: 2024	2025-2030	
		Report to the Storting No. 7 (2024–2025) On Sexual Harassment	Ministry of Culture and Equality	Adoption: 2024	2024-open-ended	
		Equality and Anti-Discrimination Act	Ministry of Culture and Equality; Equality and Anti-Discrimination Ombud (LDO); Anti-Discrimination Tribunal	Adoption: 2017; Amendments: 2024	2017-open-ended	
		Working Environment Act	Ministry of Labour and Social Inclusion	Adoption: 2005; Amendments: 2025	2005- open-ended	
		The Penal Code	Ministry of Justice and Public Security	Adoption: 2005; Amendments: 2025	2005- open-ended	
		Mandate for the Committee for Gender Balance and Diversity in Research and Higher Education	The Ministry of Education	Adoption: 2004	Previous mandate 2022-25 Next mandate 2026-29	

APPENDIX 3. DEDICATED INSTRUMENTS IN DETAIL

Country	Main Instrument Title	Public Consultation	Stakeholders Involved	Types of Misconduct Covered	Types of Institutions Covered	Budget	Zero-Tolerance Code of Conduct Endorsed?
Belgium	Decree on Transgressive Behaviour in Higher Education	No	Researchers/experts on GBV, Student initiatives and associations, Ministries/ government departments, Representatives from 1 university college and 1 university, contact point/mediation service the Genderkamer	Violence, Transgressive behaviour, Sexual harassment (“unwanted sexual behaviour”), Harassment/bullying (the term “pesterijen” does not necessarily have a sexual component in Dutch)”	Public HEIs from the Flemish authority	No	Not applicable (adopted prior to 2024)
France	National Action Plan Against Sexist and Sexual Violence in Higher Education and Research	Yes	Specialised NGOs, Student initiatives and associations Staff organisations/trade unions, Ministries/government departments	Sexist and sexual violence (encompassing sexual or sexist insult or defamation, sexist contempt, dissemination of messages contrary to decency, image capture and dissemination of indecent images, sexual exhibition, sexual harassment, sexual assault and rape)	Public HEIs, Private/non-public HEIs, Public-Private HEIs, Public RIs, Private RIs	Yes	Not applicable (adopted prior to 2024)
Ireland	Safe, Respectful, Supportive and Positive: Ending Sexual Violence and Harassment in Irish Higher Education Institutions	Yes	Specialised NGOs, Student initiatives and associations, Researchers/experts on GBV, Ministries/government departments	Sexual misconduct is any form of unwelcome behaviour of a sexual nature that may be subject to disciplinary proceedings. This includes crimes of sexual violence, sexual cyberbullying of any kind including non-consensual taking and/or sharing of intimate images, creating,	Public HEIs	Yes	Not applicable (adopted prior to 2024)

				accessing, viewing or distributing child pornography material online or offline, stalking behaviours whether online or offline in a sexual context, and any verbal or physical harassment in a sexual context.			
Netherlands	Integral Policy on Social Safety in Higher Education and Science	Yes	Researchers/experts on gender-based violence, Student initiatives and associations, Staff organisations/trade unions, Survivor groups, Ministries/government departments, Umbrella organisations of the HEI	(sexual) transgressive behaviour, abuse of power, discrimination, racism and intimidation	Public HEIs	Yes	Not applicable (adopted prior to 2024)
Portugal	Law n. 61/2023	Information not available	Information not available	Harassment, Sexual violence	Public HEIs, Private/non-public HEIs, Public-Private HEIs	Information not available	Not applicable (adopted prior to 2024)